

CoastObs

D3.8: Higher level products report

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Author list:

Name	Organisation
Steef Peters	Water Insight
Kathrin Poser	Water Insight
Annelies Hommersom	Water Insight
Lazaros Spaias	Water Insight
Yuting Lin	Water Insight
Anne-Laure Barillé	Bio-Littoral
Nicolas Harin	Bio-Littoral
Pierre Gernez	Universite de Nantes
Laurent Barillé	Universite de Nantes
Laura Zoffoli	Universite de Nantes
Tony van der Hiele	HZ University of Applied Sciences
Jasper van Houcke	HZ University of Applied Sciences
Luis Gonzalez Vilas	Universidad de Vigo
Jesus Torres Palenzuela	Universidad de Vigo

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CoastObs Project

CoastObs is an EU H2020 funded project that aims at using satellite remote sensing to monitor coastal water environments and to develop a user-relevant platform that can offer validated products to users including monitoring of seagrass and macroalgae, phytoplankton size classes, primary production, and harmful algae as well as higher level products such as indicators and integration with predictive models.

phytoplankton

seagrass

harmful algal blooms

primary production

To fulfil this mission, we are in dialogue with users from various sectors including dredging companies, aquaculture businesses, national monitoring institutes, among others, in order to create tailored products at highly reduced costs per user that stick to their requirements.

With the synergistic use of Sentinel-3 and Sentinel-2, CoastObs aims at contributing to the sustainability of the Copernicus program and assisting in implementing and further fine-tuning of European Water Quality related directive.

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Water Insight BV. (WI)

**UNIVERSITY OF
STIRLING**

The University of Stirling (USTIR)

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delle Ricerche

Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche (CNR)

UNIVERSITÉ DE NANTES

Universite de Nantes (UN)

**UNIVERSITY
OF APPLIED SCIENCES**

HZ University of Applied Sciences (HZ)

UNIVERSIDADE
DE VIGO

Universidad de Vigo (UVIGO)

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1 Summary

Objective:

Based on the analysis of the users' spatial, temporal and content-level information needs, CoastObs develops higher level aggregated products from the basic products. These products can consist of (a combination of) spatial and temporal aggregation, classification and integration with additional data and tools, such as growth models for shellfish.

Rationale:

Based on earlier experience and user contacts CoastObs set out to develop several types of services, namely operational monitoring, environmental reporting, spatial suitability analysis and historic analysis. The first service type, operational monitoring, is mainly in the domain of near real time monitoring and requires basic products like a Chlorophyll-a map. The other service types require higher level (aggregated) products combining basic products over longer time spans.

A preliminary overview table of higher level products was presented in the CoastObs proposal and is repeated here (Table 1).

Some higher level products can be constructed based on spatial and temporal aggregations of basic products (such as seasonal averages or averages per water body), combination of individual products (for example, a combination of Chl-a and TSM is a good indicator for food quality for mussels), extraction of spatio-temporal features (such as phytoplankton bloom phenology or rates of coastal erosion and accretion) and indicators based on classification and comparison to reference conditions.

Another type of higher level products is based on the integration of EO data with predictive models. Two examples are the integration of EO-derived Chl-a and TSM maps into ecophysiological mussel models, in order to yield spatially explicit predictions of mussel growth as well as the prediction of phytoplankton blooms. The phytoplankton bloom models regularly incorporate satellite imagery into the prediction of the bloom occurrence and dynamics.

CoastObs works on such a model to provide predictive solutions of HABs as example for the higher level products part of the service portfolio.

Table 1: Preliminary overview of higher-level products

Product	Definition	Purpose	Basic products used
Phytoplankton bloom phenology	Timing of the onset, length and intensity of phytoplankton blooms	Monitoring of the effects of eutrophication, mitigation measures actions, and climate change, better targeted in situ sampling schemes	Chl-a maps, PP maps, HAB/indicator species maps
WFD indicators	Classification of a water body as having High, Good, Moderate, Poor, or Bad water quality	Simplification of WFD reporting for the user	EO based aggregated data products and maps (Chl-a, PC, transparency), in situ measurements (Chl-a, PC, transparency)
Coastal erosion and accretion monitoring	Trace changes in the shoreline due to erosion and accretion	Support local risk assessment and shoreline management	TSM maps, shoreline maps
Phytoplankton and Sediment Source identification and prediction	Trace sources of plankton blooms	Allow the user to take measures to reduce e.g. nutrient influx	Chl-a and turbidity maps Model predictions
Spatial suitability	Long-term record of spatial distribution of certain WQ parameters	Identify areas that are particularly suitable for a certain type of use (e.g. mussel aquaculture)	Chl-a and TSM maps, PSC, PP, SST

2 Introduction

This report will present in subsequent chapters the main types of higher level products that are being developed in CoastObs.

Ch 3: Phytoplankton bloom phenology

CH 4: Sediment plume morphology

CH 5: Coastal erosion and accretion

CH 6: Water Framework Directive reporting

CH 7: Integration with modelling: mussel culture potential

CH 8: Integration with modelling: harmful algae bloom forecasting

Each chapter will present a rationale and background, the input data for the product generation, main methods used and examples of results so far.

3 Phytoplankton bloom phenology

3.1 Rationale

The study of the phytoplankton seasonal cycle (phenology) is relevant to understanding the functioning of the marine ecosystem. Phytoplankton bloom phenology addresses the question: when is how much of the phytoplankton where? Changes in phenology affect ecosystem functioning and productivity and have an impact on higher trophic levels and – via fisheries and aquaculture – on economic activities and food production. Phenology is also a sensitive indicator of climate change. Therefore, phytoplankton bloom phenology is of interest to environmental monitoring and management authorities as well as to aquaculture and fisheries regulators and producers. So far, phenological indicators have not been readily available, therefore uptake of this information has been limited.

3.2 Background

The timing of phytoplankton blooming depends on many physical, chemical, and biological factors such as light exposure, mixing, availability of nutrients, respiration and predation (grazing) rates (Cabre et al., 2016). Phenology metrics, including the timing of phytoplankton growth initiation, maximum amplitude, time of the peak, termination and duration are considered as ecological indicators that represent objective and quantitative measurements for evaluating the condition of marine ecosystems and their response to environmental change (Gittings et al., 2019).

Because phytoplankton constitute the base of the trophic net in marine environments, changes in phenology affecting the growing season have impacts in ecosystem functioning and productivity. Phenology is also a sensitive indicator of climate change. More and more studies are now providing evidence that the plankton's distribution, abundance and seasonality is altering as their habitat warms, uncoupling the marine food chain. Effects on bloom phenology are not straight forward and might show large regional differences (e.g. Salgado-Hernanza et al, 2019). These changes to the timing of the phytoplankton bloom associated with climate warming are expected to have impacts on the marine food web and carbon cycling. Studies have shown that fluctuations in the abundance, size and composition of phytoplankton communities result in long-term changes in the numbers of large, commercially important fish, such as North Sea cod (Beaugrand et al, 2004). Other examples include larval haddock, whose survival is associated with an early spring bloom, permitting the greatest overlap between larvae and their food (Platt et al, 2003; Petric and all, 2014). Comparable studies have also

documented an association between earlier timing of the spring bloom and the hatching and size of young shrimp in the North Atlantic (Fuentes-Yaco et al., 2007). Temperate marine environments may be particularly vulnerable to these changes because the recruitment success of higher trophic levels is highly dependent on synchronization with planktonic production (Edwards and Richardson, 2004). Remote sensing of ocean colour constitutes an invaluable tool for construction of consistent time series over large areas and long periods of time.

3.3 Input data

3.3.1 CoastObs basic products

Chl-a and possibly also primary production. The choice of satellite data base and algorithm to derive Chl-a will depend on the study area according to the characteristics of its water column and quantity of years available for orbital data, in a way to warranty a consistent ocean colour pool series.

3.3.2 Additional data

In situ Chl-a data for validation of the satellite derived Chl-a products

3.4 Methods

Before the estimation of bloom metrics, preparation of the time series is required and crucial to warranty reliable results. Usually, the raw satellite time series include gaps, noise, outliers, and multi-modal bloom distributions and demand some pre-processing to mitigate their impacts on the derived bloom phenology (Rolinski et al., 2007; Ferreira et al., 2014). Various interpolation, smoothing and curve fitting methods have been used before computing the indices listed above, e.g. shifted Gaussian fitting (e.g. Platt et al., 2009b), low pass filtering (Wiltshire et al., 2008), fast Fourier transform (Brody et al., 2013) and generalized linear model (Vargas et al., 2009). Generally speaking, if a time series is uni-modal, with high frequency of sampling and only few outliers, all methods perform well. Otherwise, more advanced and flexible approaches with less assumption of distribution pattern would perform better (Ji et al., 2010). Different pre-processing methods will be tested according to the Chl-a time series characteristics.

A variety of indices have been developed to describe the evolution of phytoplankton blooms from satellite data based on the analysis of time series of chlorophyll, including timing of initiation, peak or decline, bloom duration, and bloom magnitude either as maximum concentrations or time-integrated biomass (Ji et al., 2010). The most appropriate

phytoplankton metric depends on the question being investigated, but also on geography and the dominant forcing mechanisms. For identifying ecosystem responses to climate change and links to physical forcing, a wide range of possible metrics should be explored (Vargas et al., 2009), whereas for investigations into the interactions between trophic levels, different indices can be useful depending on the specific interaction under investigation (Ji et al., 2010).

Besides different metrics, also different methods have been proposed to derive the chosen phenology metrics from remote sensing data. For example, for deriving bloom initiation, Ji et al. (2010) identify three broad categories of methods: (1) **thresholds based on chlorophyll concentration**, (2) **thresholds based on cumulative chlorophyll** and (3) **rate of change methods**. **Threshold methods based on chlorophyll concentration** define bloom initiation as the time at which a chlorophyll time series crosses a fixed or variable threshold, often 5% above the median (e.g. Siegel et al., 2002; Racault et al., 2012; Cole et al., 2012). **Threshold methods based on cumulative chlorophyll concentration** identify a bloom as the time at which a cumulative summation of chlorophyll concentration crosses a threshold percentile of the total biomass (e.g. Greve et al., 2005;). For an example see Figure 1. Rate of change methods estimate bloom initiation from the point of most rapid increase on a chlorophyll time series along one year (e.g. Sharples et al., 2006; Rolinski et al., 2007; White et al., 2009). According to Brody et al. (2013), threshold-based methods can be especially appropriate for investigating the match or mismatch between phytoplankton and upper trophic levels (e.g. Koeller et al., 2009). The **rate of change methods**, on the contrary, can be useful for studying the links between seasonal physical or biological conditions and phytoplankton phenology (Brody et al., 2013). In the case of methods based on cumulative thresholds, they are quite flexible depending on the cumulative threshold chosen, but they are sensitive to the date used for the start of the time series and thus cannot be implemented at the basin scale using a fixed start date (Brody et al., 2013). It should be noted that threshold-based and cumulative threshold methods can be biased by long-term bloom intensity trends, whereas rate-of-change-based methods are not (Groetsch et al., 2016).

Ideally, a phenology metric should be accurate, precise, and simultaneously sensitive to the underlying environmental processes (physical or biological) (Ferreira et al., 2014). Ferreira et al. (2014) argue that there are important differences in the inherent variability of phenology metrics and in their precision. They observe that the precision of many of these metrics is poor and is of greater concern than their lack of accuracy. They found the cumulative distribution to best satisfy all criteria, but also acknowledge that further investigation of pre-processing could still improve the results of the indicators.

Figure 1 Example of deriving phenology metrics using a threshold method

According to Ferreira et al. (2014) the choice of phenology metric should be determined by the research question being addressed, and whether the metrics are equally robust to observational noise, missing data, and bloom amplitude. Our service is expected to produce yearly maps of the following phenology metrics for the dominant phytoplankton bloom, subject to further discussion with the end-users:

- Start timing (day of year)
- End timing (day of year)
- Length (days)
- Peak timing (day of year)
- Base concentration (mg m⁻³)
- Maximum concentration (mg m⁻³)
- Amplitude (mg m⁻³)
- Number of distinct blooms per year

Additionally, for each of the phenology parameters, a trend analysis will be performed over the total period covered by the service on a pixel-by-pixel basis based on the existence and significance of a linear trend. The results of the trend analysis will be presented as a trend map per parameter.

For reporting regions or individual pixels, averages of the phenology metrics will be calculated and presented as graphs (an example is shown in Figure 2).

Figure 2 Example plot of three phenological indicators for a 11-year time period

The CoastObs web mapping application will present the data products as interactive maps to allow for exploring the spatial variability of phytoplankton phenology. For preselected regions and possibly for each pixel, it will also be possible to retrieve time series of the phenological parameters interactively by clicking on the parameter maps. This will allow to detect the interannual variability and trends in phenology per region. After the growing season, a new data layer will be added for each phenology metric, and the trend maps and time series plots will be updated to include the new data.

3.5 Results

An example of a map showing one phenology metric is given in Figure 3. For this map a data series of CMEMS Chlorophyll-a products were combined and processed to calculate the amplitude of phytoplankton blooms in the North Sea and North East Atlantic region. The amplitude of the bloom was observed heterogeneous in the example area, ranging between 0.1-20 mg m⁻³. Higher values were higher in coastal areas, together with in the North portion around Greenland and South-west off-shore of UK, and probably associated with a higher loads of nutrients.

Figure 3 Example of a Chlorophyll-a phenology product: the amplitude of blooms in a certain year derived in this case from CMEMS Chlorophyll-a products.

3.6 Conclusions and recommendations

The advantage of the CoastObs raster array processing approach will be that phenology products can be made on a regular basis using the available Chl-a maps produced in NRT and adjusted for different studies areas and according to end-users demands. Some further research needs to be done on how to calculate phenology metrics in a scientifically sound manner, especially under conditions where cloudiness introduces gaps in the space-time series.

4 Sediment plume morphology

4.1 Rationale

The accurate measurement of suspended particulate matter (SPM) concentration in coastal waters is of crucial importance for coastal ecosystem management. This topic is particularly important in the Loire estuary area where the turbid plume is generated by the longest French river. During the first part of the CoastObs project, several users interested in the plume's monitoring and characterization have been identified and met by Bio-Littoral and the University of Nantes in order to precisely identify which satellite products could be useful for them. In 2015, the coastal area of the Loire estuary has been designated as a *Natura2000* perimeter managed by the **French Agency of Biodiversity**. The agency requested the monitoring of the export of SPM from the estuary to the coastal ocean, and the assessment of its impact on the primary production. Predicting the extent and the direction of the Loire turbid plume is also necessary for the assessment of anthropogenic impacts of industrial activities generating turbidity at the vicinity of the mouth of the estuary. **The Port of Nantes-Saint-Nazaire** would like to know if dredging operations contribute or not to the turbid plume. **Private companies extracting marine sediments** have leases in front of the Loire estuary area. They want to compare the turbid plumes generated by their activity with the natural plume of the river. Using a time-series of high resolution Sentinel-2 SPM data from 2017 – 2018, simple descriptors of the plume morphology have been tested and related to environmental conditions (river flow, wind, tidal regime) to understand the mechanisms governing the turbid plume dynamics.

4.2 Background

4.2.1 Study area

4.2.1.1 Loire estuary

Situated on the French Atlantic coast, the coastal area of the Loire estuary extends 100 km seaward from the river's mouth at Saint Nazaire (Figure 4). It is one of the three largest French estuaries, with the Seine and the Gironde. With 118 000 km² the hydrographic basin of the estuary is covering about one fifth of the French territory. This macrotidal and highly turbid system plays the double role of an ecologically important wetland and an axis of economic development. The Loire river drains a mean annual flow of 825 m³ s⁻¹, with a seasonal flow rate (Figure 3). The maximum water discharge is generally recorded during winter and spring (up to 4000 m³ s⁻¹), whereas the lowest flows occur in summer (100 m³ s⁻¹). Tides propagate to as

much as 35 km upstream to Nantes during periods of low river flow. Concerning the transport of cohesive sediments in the estuary and associated turbidity dynamics, numerical modelling studies showed that the turbidity maximum zone is large during spring tides, whereas thick fluid mud layers appear on neap tides (Le Hir & Thouvenin, 1994). The Loire estuary is extremely turbid, with surface SPM concentration varying from 10 to more than 2000 g m⁻³ in the high-turbidity zones.

Figure 4 Location of the region of interest (ROI), Loire estuary area

4.2.2 Turbidity remote sensing in the Loire estuary

Since early Landsat observations of the turbid discharge of the Mississippi waters in the Louisiana Bight (Rouse & Coleman, 1976), satellite remote sensing has been widely used to detect SPM concentration in the world's main estuaries (Mertes et al., 1993; Forget & Ouillon, 1998; Shi & Kirby, 2003; Doxaran et al., 2006; Gernez et al., 2015). A variety of inversion algorithms have been developed in the last decades (Freeman et al., 2017), and it is out of the scope of the present document to review and evaluate them all, all the more as their accuracy is highly dependent on the performance of the atmospheric correction (Caballero et al., 2018). In turbid near-shore areas, the water reflectance signal tends to saturate due to high level of reflectance caused by high SPM concentrations in the visible and near-infrared spectral regions,

thus challenging the atmospheric correction and the application of inversion algorithms (Doxaran et al., 2002).

In the Loire and Gironde estuary, the combination of the ACOLITE atmospheric correction with a band-switching algorithm has been recently demonstrated to avoid saturation effects and to accurately compute SPM concentration (Novoa et al., 2017). This band switching SPM algorithm was initially developed for Landsat8-OLI, and has been recalibrated to Sentinel2-MSI (Gernez et al., 2017). The approach used here to retrieve the concentration of SPM in the Loire estuary is thus based on a Sentinel2-specific regional algorithm, building on previous published methods (Novoa et al., 2017; Gernez et al., 2017).

An additional validation exercise has been performed in the frame of CoastObs project, using in situ turbidity measurements from a regional monitoring network¹. One year of automated high-frequency in situ data were extracted in 2016 and compared with the corresponding CoastObs SPM product, using the matchup procedure described in Gernez et al. (2015). The result proved satisfactory (Figure 5), and outperformed other tested SPM algorithms recently developed for turbid coastal waters (i.e. Han et al., 2016, not shown).

Figure 5 Validation of CoastObs SPM basic product using in situ matchups available in 2016 from the regional turbidity monitoring network (N = 23, $r^2 = 0.89$). The

¹ <http://www.loire-estuaire.org/dif/do/network>

performance of one of the most-commonly used SPM algorithm (Nechad et al., 2010) is also shown as an example.

4.3 Input data

4.3.1 CoastObs basic product

Sentinel2 Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) concentration

4.3.2 Additional data (hydrometeorological data)

River flow rate. The Loire daily flow rate was recorded at St Nazaire station. The hydrological information was obtained from “Banque Hydro service” (Source: DREAL Pays-de-Loire / HYDRO-MEDDE/DE; <http://www.hydro.eaufrance.fr/>).

Tide conditions. The tide cycle and amplitude were obtained from the site of the “Service Hydrographique et Océanographique de la Marine” (<http://www.SHOM.fr>) using the Port of St Nazaire as a reference. The tidal amplitude varies from about 2 m during neap tide, to about 6 m during spring tide. It is quantified using the unit-less French metric of “tide coefficient”, varying from < 40 (lowest amplitude during neaps low) to 120 (highest amplitude during springs high). The phase of the tidal cycle was computed as the time between low tide and satellite overpass. The images are considered at high or low tide when they are in a time slot of 1h 30 min before and after the tide, or are classified as belonging to flood or ebb tide. For statistical analyses, the tidal phase was coded as High tide=1, Ebb tide=2, Low tide=3, Flood tide=4.

Wind conditions. Daily data of wind speed and direction measured at the nearest weather station (Montoir / St Nazaire) were collected from the French weather forecast agency (source: www.infoclimat.fr). The wind speed was taken for the same day than the Sentinel2 acquisition, as well as for the day before. For statistical analyses, the wind direction/sector was coded as West=1, South=2, North=3, East=4.

4.4 Methods

4.4.1 Processing of Sentinel2 data (basic SPM product)

Two full years of Sentinel2 data were processed (2017-2018). All tiles covering the study area (tile #T30TWT) were previsualised and selected when the region of interest (ROI) was mostly free of clouds. A total of 39 cloud-free images has been initially selected. Level1 Sentinel2 data have then been downloaded and processed to Level2 by Water Insight, and provided to BL and

UN for the development of higher-level products. Sentinel2 images were atmospherically corrected using the ACOLITE software² to obtain the water leaving reflectance, $\rho_w(\lambda)$. Land, clouds and sunglint were excluded in this product. The ACOLITE-derived water leaving reflectance $\rho_w(\lambda)$ was then converted in SPM concentration using a band-switching algorithm initially developed for Landsat8-OLI (Novoa et al., 2017) and further recalibrated for Sentinel2 (Gernez et al., 2017). Due to remaining clouds and sunglint impact on the SPM outputs, only 30 maps were eventually used for the plume analysis. We note that, due to the cloud cover restriction, periods of low river flows in summer and fall were oversampled compared to the periods of high water discharge in winter (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Temporal variation of the Loire river flow (St Nazaire station) from 2017 - 2018. The red squares indicate the date of Sentinel-2 images eventually selected and processed for the turbid plume higher-level product.

4.4.2 Statistical analysis (higher-level product)

For all Sentinel2 turbidity map, each pixel was classified into four turbidity classes according to the SPM concentration: < 15 , $15-50$, $50-200$, and $>200 \text{ g m}^{-3}$ (Figure 7). Two metrics were then tested to characterize the plume's morphology: its surface area (number of pixels per class) and

² <https://odnature.naturalsciences.be/remsem/software-and-data/acolite>

its length, measured seaward using the distance from a reference point (Figure 8), for each turbidity class.

Figure 7 Example of turbidity classification in the Loire estuary area (Sentinel2 image from 12 April 2017), showing the four classes of SPM concentration: < 15, 15-50, 50-200, and >200 g m^{-3} .

For each metric, the four dependent variables (one plume metric for each turbidity class) were used to calculate a statistical distance between each date. The statistical distance was then used to obtain clusters corresponding to different environmental conditions. The statistical analysis based on the plume's surface area (number of pixels per class) did not provide consistent clustering of the different dates/environmental conditions (not shown). The metric retained here was therefore the distance from a reference point. The values of the four turbidity classes were used to calculate the Euclidian distance between each date and obtain clusters that were significantly different with a type I error of 5%. The significance of the clustering was tested with the SIMPROF and ANOSIM tests available in PRIMER software (Clarke & Warwick, 2001). The relationship between the turbidity data and the environmental

conditions (tide, wind, and river flow) was estimated with a correlation test between the two matrices of data using the BEST procedure (Clarke & Warwick, 2001). The statistical significance of the relationships between the Euclidian distance of dates and the normalized environmental data was tested, and the variables contributing to these relationships were identified by a stepwise calculation. Then, for each significant environmental variable, box-plots graphs were plotted to characterize the clusters, and non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis tests were performed, followed by pairwise comparisons, to identify statistically significant differences.

Figure 8 Example of plume morphology analysis (Sentinel2 image from 21 Feb. 2018). The plume metric is computed using the maximum distance from a reference point (in green) along a seaward trajectory (black line) for each turbidity class, here: [15-50], [50-200], and >200 g m^{-3} . Note that in this example the southern part of the Loire's turbid plume is adjacent with the turbid waters of Bourgneuf Bay. The distance was therefore measured using the western boundary of the plume.

4.5 Results

4.5.1 Plume morphology

Four statistical clusters of the plume morphology were obtained using the Euclidian distance between each date (SIMPROF & ANOSIM, $P < 0.05$, Figure 9), with the length of the plume for each turbidity class as a descriptor of the SPM distribution in the Loire estuary.

Figure 9 Statistical clustering of the plume morphology. The x-axis corresponds to the Sentinel2 acquisition date. The y-axis corresponds to the Euclidian distance between the plume's metric of each date. The red dashed lines represents the clusters that are not statistically different.

The clusters correspond to the following plume morphology (Figure 10):

- **Group a) Small plume**, varying from 0 – 15 km for the highest turbidity class ($SPM > 200 \text{ g m}^{-3}$) to 30 – 45 km for the lowest turbidity class ($SPM < 15 \text{ g m}^{-3}$).
- **Group b) Medium plume**, varying from 0 – 31 km for the highest turbidity class ($SPM > 200 \text{ g m}^{-3}$) to 41 – 58 km for the lowest turbidity class ($SPM < 15 \text{ g m}^{-3}$).
- **Group c) Large plume**, varying from 36 – 43 km for the highest turbidity class ($SPM > 200 \text{ g m}^{-3}$) to 55 – 66 km for the lowest turbidity class ($SPM < 15 \text{ g m}^{-3}$).
- **Group d) Extreme plume**, exceeding 45 km for the highest turbidity class ($SPM > 200 \text{ g m}^{-3}$) and 78 km for the lowest turbidity class ($SPM < 15 \text{ g m}^{-3}$).

SPM ($\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)

< 15	15 - 50	50,01 - 200	> 200	NoData

Figure 10 Sentinel2-derived maps of turbidity over the study area. The maps are sorted as the results of the cluster analysis of the plume morphology, with groups a, b, c and d corresponding to small, medium, large and extreme plumes, respectively. Land, clouds and sunglint are represented in grey.

The number of image per cluster varies from 2 (group **d**) to 14 (group **b**). Though the low number of images classified in group **d** could be explained by the rarity of the extreme plumes, it nevertheless limits the statistical significance of the analysis. More Sentinel2 images should be processed to strengthen the results, and the addition of Landsat8 data should also be considered to increase the number of cloud-free observations.

4.5.2 Influence of environmental factors on plume morphology

The river flow, tidal range, and wind speed (for the same day than the satellite acquisition) all significantly contributed to explain the turbidity variability between the four morphology groups (BEST statistical test, correlation coefficient $r = 0.549$, p -value < 0.1). The other environmental parameters, namely the wind direction, tidal phase, and wind speed of previous day, did not significantly contributed to the plume variability. Note that due to the overall synchronicity between Sentinel2 acquisition time (around 11:10 UT for the study area) and the concomitant tidal phase (11:00 UT either corresponds to low tide during springs, or to high tide during neaps), the influence of tidal phase is very challenging to assess using sun-synchronous satellite remote sensing, as previously acknowledged in the literature (Eleveld et al., 2014).

The range of variability of the discriminant environmental drivers has then been analysed for each group of plume morphology (Figure 11). The three variables (river flow, tidal range, wind speed) showed statistical significant differences between the four plume morphology groups (Kruskall-Wallis, $P < 0.05$). The river flows appears as a dominant driver of the plume morphology. There is a striking difference between group **a** (small plumes, river flow $< 500 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and group **d** (extreme plumes, river flow $> 1700 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), as well as an overall increase in river flow from the smaller to the larger plumes. The tidal range also displayed a conspicuous influence on the plume morphology. Small and medium plumes (morphology groups **a**, **b**) are generally observed during neap tides (median tidal coefficient < 70) whereas the large and extreme plumes (groups **c**, **d**) systematically occurred during spring tides (tidal coefficient > 80). An overall gradient in wind speed is also observed along the increase in the plume's length, with the median wind speed varying from $< 10 \text{ km h}^{-1}$ to $> 15 \text{ km h}^{-1}$ from group **a** (small plumes) to **d** (extreme plumes).

Figure 11 Box-plots showing the environmental variability for each morphology group, in terms of river flow, tidal range and wind speed. The thick line represents the median, the rectangle corresponds to the range between the 25% and 75% percentiles, and the lower and higher segments represent the minimum and maximum value, respectively.

4.6 User feedback

The results presented here being preliminary, the higher-level products for plume morphology have not been yet distributed to the users. The processing of additional Sentinel2 data is planned for October – December 2019, and the increase of observations is expected to strengthen the results. Upcoming meetings with the users are scheduled in early 2020.

4.7 Conclusions and recommendations

A method to compute higher-level products of plume morphology has been presented here for the Loire estuary. The results, while preliminary due to the limited number of Sentinel2 cloud-free observations in 2017 and 2018, are consistent with similar studies performed for the Rhône (Gangloff et al., 2017), Gironde (Constantin et al., 2018), and Po estuaries (Manzo et al., 2018), which were based on longer satellite time-series. Despite this limitation, a satisfactory framework is provided here to objectively characterize the plume morphology and disentangle the confounding effects of the various environmental factors on the export of SPM into the coastal ocean, in order to answer the requests of the French Agency of Biodiversity, of the Port of Nantes-Saint-Nazaire, and of private companies extracting marine sediments.

5 Coastal erosion and accretion

5.1 Rationale

Coastal and especially estuarine environments are characterized by high sediment dynamics. The distribution of sediments over an area will change depending on discrete events (high river run-off, spring-tides) or gradual events (such as sea level rise) resulting in changes in coastline. Erosion will occur in high flow conditions and accretion in the opposite situation. A typical example of a dynamical coastal system with continuous coastline changes is a bird foot delta. Remote sensing can be used to map changes in coastline and support the local risk assessment and shoreline management. In the Netherlands, experiments are ongoing to actively manage the coastline as a counterstrategy to sea level rise and the accompanying increased risk of high waves and floods.

5.2 Background

The Dutch/German Ems estuary provides a clear example of a system that has experienced a continuous ecological degradation and it has been used here as a case study. Such degradation comes mainly from its strong artificial morphology, high levels of turbidity, extended periods of anoxia in certain zones and a limited quality and quantity of native estuarine habitats inside the whole system. In general, the Ems ecosystem function can be discussed by distinguishing two main themes, namely the abiotic environment such as morphology and water quality, and the biotic environment, which relates to the habitats and species living those habitats. Although many studies have been done in different disciplines to assess its dynamic and function changes, there are still some knowledge gaps for the ecological improvement, such as continuous long-term monitoring of spatial distribution patterns (Bos et al., 2013), which may be easily achieved by using remote sensing techniques. For improving ecological restoration, it is important to have both spatial and temporal information. The recently launched satellites, such as Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 give an opportunity to expand further long-term assessment of estuary characteristics.

The Ems estuary is part of the European Wadden Sea. The surface of the Ems estuary is approximately 500 km², including a fresh water tidal area in the Ems of about 37 km² (Baretta and Ruardij, 1988). The geographical extent of the Ems estuary stretches from the island Borkum until the weir near the German village Pogum (Figure 12). The historical formation of the Ems estuary can be traced back to the last two glaciations. The river valleys were formed during periods of high river run-off and during periods when the sea trespassed through until

it was inundated. Later on, a large amount of sediments was supplied by the river and the delta was formed. The final shape of the Ems estuary was formed by effects of sediment supply, storm surges and anthropogenic effects such as land reclamation. This process continued until the present day resulting in the Ems estuary and Dollard bay as it is now.

Figure 12 Study area - Ems estuary

Talke and De Swart (2006) summarized hydrodynamics and morphology related scientific measurements of the Ems estuary. The Ems estuary has been assessed by long term monitoring programs by Germany and Dutch governmental agencies that have occurred in past and currently running monitoring programs. The long term monitoring of velocity, sediment concentration, turbidity, salinity, water level, temperature, pH and oxygen concentration have been performed at 9 locations in 3-30 minutes intervals by NLWKN (Niedersächsischer Landesbetrieb für Wasserwirtschaft, Küsten- und Naturschutz) and WSA (The Waterways and Shipping Board) Emden. In addition, RWS (Rijkswaterstaat) performed sampling at Borkum and in the Dollard for measuring biological and chemical parameters at biweekly to monthly intervals. The BOA project, funded by NWO (The Netherlands

Organisation for Scientific Research) and running from 1995 to 1997, studied physical and biological processes affecting mud in shallow water and intertidal areas, combining instrumentation on mudflats with a bridge across a tidal channel near the Herringsplaat. Moreover, the BOA project that ran with the European Community project INTRMUD (The

Morphological Behaviour of Intertidal Mudflats)³, studied the morphological behaviour of intertidal mudflats. Other long-term measurement projects are Emssperwerk baseline measurement⁴ (since 31st of March, 2001), BOEDE project⁵(measured during the 1970's and early 1980's), and BIOGEST⁶ (measured the Ems estuary in July 1997).⁷

5.2.1 Historical information on morphological changes

To explore the dynamics in coast morphology of the Ems estuary, Herrling and Niemeyer (2007) used the historical and the present states of the estuarine topography data. They concluded that the Ems-Dollard estuary experienced a dramatic change by the effect of natural processes and anthropogenic effects from 1989 to 2005. For instance, storm surges caused enormous coastal retreat which was reclaimed by coastal inhabitants, and the result of deepening and streamlining of the channel caused long-term morpho-dynamical processes. Within the Ems-Dollard, outer reaches of the Ems estuary and tidal flat areas remained nearly constant between 1860 and 2005, but subtidal areas of the Ems-Dollard region decreased by approximately 50%. Schoemans (2013) used a depth-averaged (2D) model and a 10-layer (3D) model to investigate the mud dynamics in the Ems-Dollard. The result shows that bottom roughness has decreased between 1945 and 1985. Both channel deepening and a reduction in bottom roughness have the same effect of a decrease in hydraulic roughness in the period 1945-2005, which causes an increase in tidal range and peak flow velocities in the Lower Ems, resulting in higher suspended sediment concentrations. Van Maren et al. (2016) used the field observations to quantify the main historical sediment sinks in the Ems estuary over the past centuries, and try to relate the sinks to changes in estuarine suspended sediment concentration. They observed an annual accumulation of sediments from the end of the 16th century to the beginning of the 20th century, but the sediments were dredged intensively in the Ems estuary from 1960 to 1994. After that, sediment dredging activities were decreased since 1990s, causing an increasing in suspended sediment concentration.

³ For more information, see: <http://www.hrwallingford.co.uk/projects/INTRMUD/>.

⁴ For more information about the result came out of these measurements, see: Conference papers by BLASI, C. & JENSEN, J. 2001. Identification and Management of Hydrological System Parameters of the Ems-Estuary. *International MEDCOAST-Conference*. Tunisia, Middle East Technical University, Ankara.

⁵ Published by VAN ES, F. & RUARDIJ, P. 1982. The use of a model to assess factors affecting the oxygen balance in the water of the Dollard. *Netherlands Journal of Sea Research*, 15, 313-330.

⁶ For more information about published paper, see: <http://labos.ulg.ac.be/oceanologie/>

⁷ BIOGEST program was measured the Ems estuary in July 1997 as part of a project investigating the emissions of biogases from European estuaries.

5.3 Input data

5.3.1 CoastObs basic products

To investigate changes in estuary morphology, and in particular ebb channel and estuary shoreline behaviour, the geomorphological history of the Ems estuaries was explored from Landsat images and 1 Sentinel-2 satellite image spanning approximately a 30-year period, from 1987 to 2016. To prototype the CoastObs coastline change service, we used the Landsat 5, 7 and 8 archive images and 1 Sentinel 2 image to investigate alterations in the shoreline in the Ems estuary. In the operational processing, Sentinel 2A and B images will also further contribute to mapping and analysis. Landsat 5 was launched on March 1, 1984 and carried the Multispectral Scanner (MSS) and the Thematic Mapper (TM) instruments. The instrument was decommissioned just a few weeks prior to the commissioning of the Landsat-8 mission. Landsat 8 was launched in February 2013. It carries two instruments: the Operational Land Imager (OLI) and the Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) (Morfitt et al., 2015). These two instruments have improved signal-to-noise (SNR) radiometric performance quantized over 12-bit dynamic range, enabling better characterization of land cover state and condition. The Landsat 8 products can be downloaded directly through the USGS global visualization viewer⁸. Sentinel 2A was launched on 23 June 2015; Sentinel 2B on March 7, 2017. Both platforms carry the Multi Spectral Imager (MSI) instrument.

An important aspect of studying coastline changes in an estuarine environment with satellite images is the tide height. Satellite acquisitions are Sun-synchronous but they are not in phase with the tide cycle. Therefore, our satellite time series included images acquired at different conditions of tide allowing us to study its effects, for example, identifying intertidal areas by the difference between the coastline at high and low tide (Table 2).

⁸ <http://glovis.usgs.gov/>

Table 2 List of different satellite data with acquisition date and time, tidal conditions at acquisition time for shoreline and tidal flat delineation

Sensor	Date of acquisition	Time (UTC)	Tide condition (m)	Water surface threshold	Purpose
Landsat-5	5-Jul-1987	9:58:26	Low tide - Ebb	NDWI > 0.2	Shoreline/Tidal flat change mapping
	20-Aug-1998	10:11:57	High tide - Ebb	MNDWI > 0.05	Tidal flat change mapping
	6-May-2006	10:25:26	Low tide - Ebb	NDWI > 0.3	Shoreline/Tidal flat change mapping
	25-Jul-2006	10:26:38	High tide - Rising	MNDWI > 0.3	Tidal flat change mapping
	4-Jul-2010	10:24:00	Low tide - Rising	NDWI > 0.1	Shoreline/Tidal flat change mapping
	18-Apr-2011	10:23:10	High tide - Rising	NDWI > 0.3	Tidal flat change mapping
Landsat-8	9-Mar-2014	10:34:01	Low tide - Rising	NDWI > 0.02	Shoreline/Tidal flat change mapping
	2-Jul-2015	10:32:51	High tide - Rising	MNDWI > 0.1	Tidal flat change mapping
Sentinel-2	1-Apr-2016	10:50:22	Low tide - Rising	NDWI > 0.01	Shoreline change mapping

5.4 Methods

To investigate coastline changes, many approaches from GIS and remote sensing methods have been proposed including: visual investigation, density slicing method, edge detection method based on a single band, and classification techniques using multiple bands (Ryu et al., 2002). Burningham (2008), for example, used different types of maps generated with aerial photographs and satellite images, along 172 years, to investigate changes in the Loughros estuary shoreline behaviour. From satellite images, the coastline can be also delineated based on the reflectance spectral information. Du et al. (2016) mapped the extent of water bodies from 10-m Sentinel-2 images using a spectral index called Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI; Gao, 1996), which is based on the green and short infrared (SWIR) bands (Equation 1). Murray et al. (2012) used the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI; Gao, 1996) to delineate the tidal flat. NDWI is a similar index than MNDWI but that uses a band in the region of the near infrared (NIR) instead the short wave infrared (SWIR). For tidal flat identification, they translated the high and low tide images to a land and water class image derived from the NDWI, and next subtracted the high tide classified image from the low tide classified image, resulting in delineation of the tidal flat.

$$MNDWI = \frac{Green_{560nm} - SWIR_{2160nm}}{Green_{560nm} + SWIR_{2160nm}} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

$$NDWI = \frac{Green_{560nm} - NIR_{865nm}}{Green_{560nm} + NIR_{865nm}} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

5.4.1 Atmospheric correction

The Case-2 Regional (C2R) Processor was applied for Landsat-8 atmospheric correction. C2R is based on the simulated relationship between inherent optical properties (IOPs) (e.g. absorption and scattering of Chlorophyll-a, CDOM, TSM) and water leaving reflectance (GLaSS_deliverable 3.3, 2014). The spectral water leaving reflectance was derived from the TOA radiance by adjusting in a first step the air pressure and ozone concentration to standard atmosphere of 1013.2 hPa and 350 DU, respectively, using metadata provided with Landsat-8 imagery (GLaSS_deliverable3.2, 2014).

For Sentinel-2 images, we applied the adapted Case 2 Regional CoastColour (C2RCC) atmospheric correction. Because of a lack of historical in-situ reflectance data, the atmospheric correction results were not validated.

5.4.2 Water surface delineation

Images were re-projected to Transverse Mercator for projecting all images to a World Geodetic System (WGS) 1984, into Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM Zone_31N) projected coordinate system using the ArcGIS projection tool.

MNDWI and NDWI were calculated for all the images. Because different images have different sensitivities as well as atmospheric conditions, it was not possible to apply a single threshold value to separate water from flat areas in the whole dataset. Instead, variable threshold values were considered here (shown in Table 2.).

5.4.3 Shoreline and tidal flat change delineation

We used the land and water class differencing method to map the shoreline and tidal flat changes (Murray et al., 2012). This method delineates the shoreline and tidal flat by subtracting pairs of a water-land classified image from NDWI or MNDWI (described in previous section). The shoreline change maps were generated by subtracting the pairs generated from low tide images from 1987 to 2016. In order to delineate the tidal flat, we defined the area inundated between the low and high tide waterline. The low tide range images were 0.5-0.8 m, while high tide images ranged from 3.4 to 3.6 m.

5.5 Results

5.5.1 Extracting water surface boundaries

Water and land surfaces were classified using image-specific thresholds (Table 2) to extract the water surface area for each year from the NDWI images. Then, the contour line of the water surface was generated for further investigate changes of water channels (Figure 15). Generally, it can be observed that water surface boundaries were clearly distinguished from the tidal flat and land areas. In some channels, very turbid waters sometimes were misclassified because of similar spectral reflectance with neighbouring riverbanks. This effect could theoretically be magnified by the adjacency effect.

Figure 13 - NDWI maps and extracted water surface boundaries from 1987 to 2016. a and b, Derived from 1987

Figure 14 (cont) - NDWI maps and extracted water surface boundaries from 1987 to 2016. c and d, Derived from 2006. e and f, Derived from 2010.

NDWI and extracted water surface boundary: 2014

NDWI and extracted water surface boundary: 2016

Figure 15 NDWI maps and extracted water surface boundaries from 1987 to 2016

5.5.2 Dynamics of coastline changes

In general, water surface boundaries showed large dynamics over the whole Ems estuary (Figure 16). By zooming in for 8 sub-regions (Figure 18), we can clearly see that in regions 1 and 2 tidal channels have shifted from 1987-2016. In regions 3 and 4, tidal flats expanded from 1987 to 2006 and 2016. Some tidal bars shifted greatly comparing early 1987 to the years after 2006.

In outer regions 5 - 8, the tidal bars moved dynamically. Some shapes of intertidal areas shifted over time, for instance on the right-top corner the intertidal flat changed from trapezoid-shape to more sharp shape. Some intertidal areas were lost over time, for instance in region 6 the right-bottom tidal flat, region 7 the top flat, and region 8 the right-mid tidal flat.

To investigate visually and quantitatively the balance between erosion and deposition, we overlaid time series images and calculated area of changed pixels. The difference between these time series images showed the erosion and deposition occurring over 30 years (Figure 18 and Table 3). It can be observed that the shallow areas in middle reaches of sand banks and mud banks have continued to undergo accretion in recent years (brown and yellow colours in Figure 18). Erosion is still ongoing especially in the region of outer reaches and the shores of barrier island and the delta flat, which might be caused by the increasing sea water filling or the velocity of water flowing through the estuary. It was observed an overall erosion from 1987-2006 and 2006-2010, while it turned to deposition from 2010-2014 mainly caused by the tidal height changes, however no able to compensate previous losses (Table 3). In a balance, the Ems estuary has experienced continuous erosion, especially in its delta.

Figure 16 Overall coastline change over the Ems estuary 1987-2016 and location of sub-regions

Region 1

Region 2

Region 3

Region 4

Region 5

Region 6

Region 7

Region 8

Figure 17 Morphology change over the Ems estuary 1987-2016 in 8 sub-regions

Figure 18 Water boundaries changes from 1987-2016

Table 3 Water boundary change from 1987-2016

Dates	Tidal height (m)	Change analysis			
		Periods differences	pixels	Condition	
1987	0.8	1987-2006 Net Gain	65,493		
2006	0.9	1987-2006 Net Loss	79,072	Loss	13,579
		2006-2010 Net Gain	11,040		
2010	0.8	2006-2010 Net Loss	103,054	Loss	92,014
		2010-2014 Net Gain	79,427		
2014	0.5	2010-2014 Net Loss	9,476	Gain	69,951
		2014-2016 Net Gain	13,318		
2016	0.6	2014-2016 Net Loss	43,779	Loss	30,461
1987-2016		1987-2016 Net Gain	64,312		
		1987-2016 Net Loss	130,403	Loss	66,091

5.5.3 Dynamics of tidal flat areal changes

In terms of investigating the tidal flat exposure condition, we mapped tidal flats by creating a land/water classified image from the water indices (NDWI and MNDWI), and subtracting the high tide classified image from the low tide classified image, resulting in delineation of the tidal flat as shown in Figure 19.

The statistical analysis revealed that the tidal flat area was about 564.08 km² in 1987, 543.68 km² in 2006, 449.50 km² in 2011, and 578.84 km² in 2015 (Table 4). The results further showed that the tidal flat area loss was 20.40 km² between 1987 and 2006, 94.18 km² between 2006 and 2011, but gained about 71.45 km² between 2011 and 2015, which might be partly because the tidal differences between 2011-2015 were much bigger than for other two years' comparison. The results indicate a decreasing trend for the Ems estuary tidal flat in the period 1987-2011, but it cannot be concluded that the flat increased again between 2011-2015.

Figure 19 Ems estuary tidal flat change from 1987-2015

Table 4 Tidal flat changes from 1987-2015

	Tidal differences	Tidal pixels	Change condition	
1987	2.7	626,757(564.08km ²)		
2006	2.6	604,089(543.68km ²)	Loss	22668(20.40km ²)
2011	2.6	499,449(449.50km ²)	Loss	104640(94.18km ²)
2015	3.1	578,840(520.96km ²)	Gain	79391(71.45km ²)

5.6 Conclusions and recommendations

In this study, we extracted the water surface boundaries by applying the water indexes NDWI and MNDWI generated from Landsat and Sentinel 2 images. The method is not always reliable under extremely high turbidity conditions, especially in the channels over the Ems-Dollard region. C2R and C2RCC were used for atmospheric correction respectively for Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2 images. The differences may influence the results of coastline mapping although the starting point is a normalized difference ratio.

The results of the satellite image analysis are probably also influenced strongly by tidal conditions and water turbidity. Additionally, the moisture conditions on the tidal flats also influences the surface water extraction. The higher the moisture content of tidal flats is, the more difficult it becomes to discriminate the water surface boundaries. The ebbing tide is expected to have more moisture on the tidal flats than rising tide, which may cause some extraction differences from the image acquisitions from the ebbing tide and rising tide. Moreover, since we used different satellite products (Landsat-5, Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2), the image sensitivities also influence the accuracy of extraction. With increasing spatial resolution such as in Sentinel-2 images, more noises or small granularity will be discriminated; at lower resolution such as Landsat-5, smoother boundaries will be extracted as compared to Sentinel-2.

The changes of the water shoreline was investigated and the results showed that shifting was dramatically happening in different parts of the Ems estuary during 30 years, from 1987 to 2016. Specifically, the outer reaches experienced sediment erosion while the middle and Dollard bay region were experiencing sediments accumulation. This was in agreement with the results found by van Maren et al. (2016) that an average annual decrease may be expected at the mouth of the estuary when the finer sand is annually extracted. However, in this study we did not classify the intertidal and subtidal areas, but the results found by Herrling and Niemeyer (2007) also indicated that there was an increase of the subtidal area in the mouth of the estuary

but decrease of the intertidal flats. With regard to a continuous time series illustrating all changes over time, we had limited time series images for comparison of the changes of the morphology, and we did not have any in-situ data about the water height, so we can only give overall general changes instead of providing accurate estimation of tidal flat changes.

The functioning of the Ems estuary is influenced by the interaction between the natural system and human impacts. In order to improve the ecosystem of the Ems-Dollard area, it is important to have a common understanding of the functioning and long-term vision on the development. Conservation and restoration of the Ems estuary are important issues these days. Most previous studies applied different types of models using field observations. Although there is a large potential for the application of remote sensing, there have been relatively few studies to give an overview of the Ems estuary changes over time with this space technique.

Even though, remote sensing techniques can contribute to monitor the dynamics of coastline changes there are still limitations for optical satellite image-based application due to the temporally limited cloud-free images. With the availability of both Sentinel 2A and B, Landsat and its future successors and also complemented by very high resolution sensors, the orbital dataset will become increasingly large and increasing the probability of obtaining cloud free images at various tidal stages. Radar images is also an option that may be explored in future stages as they have the potential of penetrate clouds producing surface images independent of weather conditions. A probable additional problem is the adjacency effect (Hommersom, 2010), which was not taken into account at all in this study. The adjacency effect is caused by high reflectances near the target pixel. Scattering processes in the atmosphere may cause some of this reflectance to be scattered into the observation path of the target pixel. Thus the observed reflectance of the target pixel becomes higher than the true value. The effect is spectral and usually observed the strongest in red and near infra-red wavelengths (but depending on the spectral properties of the target pixel surroundings and the atmosphere).

6 Water Framework Directive reporting

6.1 Rationale

The EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) applies in principle to all surface waters in the EU. The purpose is to achieve a good ecological and chemical status. For those waters for which the ecological and/or chemical status is not good, measures should be implemented to improve this status for the next WFD reporting period.

Several parameters that are used to determine the ecological status can be measured by Earth Observation, increasing the spatial representativeness of the measurements as well as in some cases the measurement frequency. Earth Observation (EO) might also help to understand the system and identify sources, which will help to take the most effective measure.

For details of the arguments for using EO data for WFD monitoring, we refer to the White Paper “Satellite-based water quality monitoring, reporting and management for the Water Framework Directive” (D6.2) (available at <https://eomores-h2020.eu/> end 2019).

6.2 Background

6.2.1 The Water Framework Directive

The purpose of the WFD is to achieve a good ecological and chemical status in all waters in EU. Such status is derived from measurements of a large range of parameters related to the water quality and ecological status. Which parameters are measured depends on the water environment (e.g. shallow turbid lakes). For each water body, a ‘reference status’ has been described, and the current status for each parameter is calculated relative to this reference. Often, several parameters measured together lead to the status of one ecological aspect. For example, for fishes, the ecological status is determined from fish species richness, the total biomass of specific species and the age structure of them, all compared to the reference status. Many EU countries use their own reference water types, their own monitoring methods and their own methods for the calculation of the ecological status.

The status of each ecological aspect is classified as ‘high’, ‘good’, ‘moderate’, ‘bad’ and ‘poor’ quality. For those waters for which the ecological and/or chemical status is less than good, measures should be carried out to improve this status for the next WFD reporting period. Similar methods apply to the chemical status. EO data can be used to measure or provide proxies for the following WFD parameters: QE1-1. Composition of phytoplankton, QE1-1

Abundance of phytoplankton, QE1-1 Biomass of phytoplankton, QE1-2 Composition of other aquatic flora, QE1-2 Abundance of other aquatic flora, QE3-1-1 Transparency, QE3-1-2 Thermal conditions, QE3-1-4 Salinity and QE3-1-5 Acidification status (see D6.2).

6.2.2 The study area for this example

For this example, we worked with Chlorophyll-a concentration (Chl-a) as a proxy for QE1-1 “Abundance of phytoplankton” for the Ems-Dollard estuary, which is a Dutch WFD reporting area. The national executive agency Rijkswaterstaat is responsible for the monitoring and WFD for this area. The Ems-Dollard is an estuary, in which the very turbid Ems river discharges on the tidal flat area of the Wadden Sea. The depth over a large portion of the area is from zero (surfacing tidal flats) to a few meters only.

In the frame of the WFD monitoring and reporting, the area was split in two water Figure 20)

1. Area NL81_2 Ems-Dollard is located in the inner part of the estuary and is classified as “O2” (Estuary with moderate tidal differences). It is considered ‘highly adjusted’, which means that for the area itself there is no reference status available (anymore), since it was adjusted too much compared to what would have been a natural status decades ago. Instead, the reference status for other but comparable, although more natural areas is used. Areas that are ‘highly adjusted’ cannot reach the ecological ‘high’ status. Then, the WFD considers the scale as “ecological potential” instead of “ecological status” and it has only four categories.
2. Area NL81_3 Ems-Dollard is located in the Wadden Sea, classified “K1” (Coastal water, open and polyhaline (salinity between 18 and 30) and considered ‘natural’.

Area NL81_2

Area NL81_3 (this just north of NL81_2)

Figure 20 WFD areas in the Dollard. Areas were taken from “factsheet OW 80 Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Milieu Rijkswaterstaat 2018-10-16-03-45-28.pdf” (www.waterkwaliteitsportaal.nl)

¹ Information from “factsheet OW 80 Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Milieu Rijkswaterstaat 2018-10-16-03-45-28.pdf” (www.waterkwaliteitsportaal.nl))

For both areas, Chl-a was used as the main parameter for Abundance of phytoplankton, although the thresholds for the different quality classes are different (Table 5). The presence of *Pheocystis* blooms is the second parameter for this aspect, however, in the upcoming reporting round the presence of *Pheocystis* blooms is discontinued as parameter. Therefore, we do not consider these blooms for this example. The thresholds for Chl-a are based on the 90-percentiles (P90) of the months March-September.

Table 5 – WFD scales for Chlorophyll-a for the Ems Dollard areas. Values are taken from Stowa (2018)

<p>The reference table for Chlorophyll P90 values for the inland area of the Ems-Dollard (type O2)</p>	<p>The reference table for Chlorophyll P90 values for the coastal area of the Ems-Dollard (type K1). The threshold between good and moderate is/was under debate.</p>																											
<p style="text-align: center;">Ecological potential</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Reference: 8 µg/l</p> <table border="0" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <tr> <td style="padding-right: 10px;">Good</td> <td style="text-align: center;">	40.52 µg/l																											
Good		12 µg/l																										
Moderate		18 µg/l																										
Bad		24 µg/l																										
Poor		36 µg/l																										
High																												
Good		6.75 µg/l																										
Moderate		15 µg/l (?)																										
Bad		20.26 µg/l																										
Poor		40.52 µg/l																										

6.3 Input data

6.3.1 CoastObs basic products

Chl-a

6.3.2 Additional data

In situ Chl-a data for satellite data validation.

Previous WFD status reports (factsheets and data downloaded from www.waterkwaliteitsportaal.nl)

6.4 Methods

6.4.1 In situ data

In situ Chl-a were downloaded from the portal [Waterinfo](#). Two in situ stations were present in each of the two areas: for the inland area 'Groote Gat noord' and 'Bocht van Watum' and for the area in the Wadden Sea 'Huibertgat oost' and 'Rottumerplaat 3km from the shore'. Even when previous WFD reports mentioned an additional monitoring station 'Dollard zwaartepunt', this station was not found and therefore, not used in this example. Inclusive P90 values were calculated for the months March-September for 2017 (for which the satellite data was available) and for 2015 (for which the WFD status reports were available).

6.4.2 Satellite data

Sentinel-2 MSI L1C data was processed with the C2X algorithm (Brockmann et al., 2016) to obtain surface reflectance. Chl-a values were retrieved through the Gons' algorithm (2005). These methods were validated within the SBIR project HBOTE ([flyer](#), in Dutch). Chl pixel values were extracted for the in situ stations to compare with satellite estimations.

Instead of calculating statistics for the area based on the in situ locations, for satellite imagery these statistics can be calculated based on the whole region. For the mean and median values in Table 6, the area as indicated in Figure 21 is used.

Figure 21 Area used to derive statistics

6.5 Results

6.5.1 Reference (in situ)

The in situ data from 2015 at the four monitoring stations showed that phytoplankton abundance status was 'bad' at station Bocht van Watum, and 'poor' at the other three stations (Figure 22).

Figure 22, Time series of concentrations at the in situ locations in 2015. The dashed lines show the 90-percentiles (one per in situ station). The colours show the WFD classes.

For 2017, in situ Chl-a were slightly higher, which would have led to a 'poor' status based on all stations (Figure 23).

Figure 23, Time series of concentrations at the in situ locations in 2017. The dashed lines show the 90-percentiles (one per in situ station). The colours show the WFD classes.

Previous WFD reports, however, were based exclusively on the 'Dollard zwaartepunt' station and for this reason, the Ems-Dollard estuary was classified as 'good ecological potential' for all reported years (2009, 2015, 2018) ("factsheet OW 80 Ministry of Infrastructure and environment Rijkswaterstaat 2018-10-16-03-45-28.pdf", available at www.waterkwaliteitsportaal.nl).

6.5.2 Satellite data

There was one match-up between in situ and satellite data on the 2nd of June 2017 (Figure 24, top left). It can be observed how much more spatial data is retrieved based on satellite information compared with the discrete stations used by in situ strategies. Note that during the image acquisition it was low tide and a large portion of the area consisted of exposed mud flats, which is greyed out in the map.

Other images of the same summer were not acquired during low tide and most of the inland part of the area is covered by water. (Figure 24b and c). However, the images of July 22 and August 4 showed that clouds can reduce the number of valid pixels to a great extent in the Ems-Dollard estuary. Comparing Chl-a in situ with retrievals from satellite over the four in situ stations, differences up to 138% could be observed. This differences can be explained by different factors. First, in situ sampling time was not the same for each station (the ship needs time to move from one site to the other) and also different from satellite acquisition. For example, in situ Bocht van Watum and Grote gat stations were collected one hour earlier and 2 hour later, respectively, compared with satellite observations. Station Huibertsgat was sampled much earlier in the morning than satellite imagery. In this area highly affected by tidal currents, measurements taken during different tide height can have a significant effect on Chl-a. Second, the sampling depths from in situ and satellite data were different. In situ sampling was performed at 1 meter from the surface while satellite measurements integrate information in the first optical depth. And third, the pixel size of Sentinel-2 ranges 10-60 m, while the in situ sample was a point measurement.

a

b

c

d

Figure 24 Chl-a maps of the Dollard area derived from Sentinel-2 satellite.

Table 6 – Chlorophyll-a concentrations on 2 June 2017.

Station	In situ	Satellite
Grote Gat noord	0 ug/l	15 ug/l
Bocht van Watum	20 ug/l	26 ug/l
Zwaartepunt	no information	no water
Huibertsgat	60 ug/l	11 ug/l
Rottumerplaat 3km	no sample	7 ug/l
mean	40 ug/l	14.7 ug/l (over the whole region)
median	40 ug/l	12.5 ug/l (over the whole region)

Extracting pixels from the in situ points from all satellite available imagery over March-September would lead to time series comparable to those shown in Figure 22 and Figure 23.

Chl-a maps derived from satellite can also be transformed into WFD classified maps to visualize the spatial ecological status of the Ems-Dollard estuary and identify areas that demand remediation tasks to retrieve ecological quality of water (e.g. Figure 25).

Figure 25. Map with the WFD status classes based on the satellite image of 2 June 2017. Only the more inland part of the Dollard is shown, to which the O₂ water type thresholds apply. Tidal flats are greyed out.

The histogram for Chl-a based on the S2 image on the 2nd of June 2017 showed that most of the pixels can be classified between moderate to good ecological status (Figure 26). Only a small percentage corresponded to bad and poor quality considering only the thresholds for K1 area.

Figure 26 Histogram of the Chl-a concentrations on June 2nd, with the WFD classification thresholds. It must be noted that the area contains two types of water (K1 for the coastal area and O2 for the inland area), which have different thresholds.

For this histogram, the thresholds for K1 are applied to the whole area.

6.6 Conclusions and recommendations

There are several parameters in the WFD which can be estimated from EO data. In our example, the Dollard area was used, which consist of two 'water types': 'Estuary with moderate tidal differences' and 'Coastal water, open and polyhaline'.

EO data has the advantage to obtain data with a large spatial extent, very frequent acquisition and at generally low cost. However, clouds might reduce the data to a significant extent, and the results might be tailored to e.g. concentrations during bright summer days. In situ sampling, on the other side, offers information collected over punctual stations and usually, at less frequent intervals. Therefore, advantages and limitations from both sources of data need to be taken into account when analysing statistics for the WFD.

There are several options for producing WFD status results based on EO data:

- Pixel extracts at specific locations, which can be treated as data points in the same way as in situ measurements (e.g. Table 6). Calculating e.g. the P90 over time provides a temporal aggregated result, which can be classified according to the WFD thresholds.
- Applying the WFD thresholds over the entire image (Figure 25).
 - This can help to understand the system: where is the status good, or moderate, or bad? Why is that the case, and which measures would therefore be the most effective?
 - It can also help to determine if the in situ sampling stations are located at representative and strategic locations.
- Spatial aggregation over an entire area (e.g. Table 6 and Figure 26). A global average over a region along a series of images can be used to calculate the P90 over time. The result is a spatial-temporal aggregate, which can be classified according to the WFD thresholds.

The choice between these approaches depends on water-management policy decisions, according to the question to be addressed. In the White Paper “Satellite-based water quality monitoring, reporting and management for the Water Framework Directive” (D6.2) it is therefore also advised to agree on methods.

7 Integration with modelling: mussel culture potential

7.1 Rationale

Blue mussels are important bivalves in Dutch coastal ecosystems, both from an ecosystem point of view as well as having important economic value. They provide filtration capacity and nutrient cycling (Smaal 1987; Smaal et al. 2001), and blue mussel beds - either natural or for farming purposes - provide a habitat with high biodiversity (Buschbaum *et al.*, 2009; Jansen *et al.*, 2017). Mussel cultivation in the Netherlands is an extensive form of aquaculture, where production mainly takes place on bottom plots in natural open water bodies. Traditionally, the designated areas for mussel cultivation in the Netherlands are the Wadden Sea and the Oosterschelde estuary. Growth and production of mussels on these bottom plots is very much dependent on natural processes. Top down processes influencing yields include predation and dislodgement. Whereas competition and food availability are bottom up processes (Capelle *et al.*, 2017). These processes influence the recruitment, growth and productivity of mussel beds in time and space. Trade-offs between loss of biomass and growth are common. Success of mussel yields therefore, are interdependent on survival, growth and the environment that mussels live in.

Growth potential for bivalves is largely determined by the availability of food particles (e.g. phytoplankton) in the water column, and food availability varies over time and space. Models relating food availability to shellfish growth can be helpful for optimization and management of shellfish culture sites and in understanding the dynamics of bivalve growth in an estuary or bay as a whole. Although models based on in situ datasets have proven to simulate shellfish growth over time well enough (Ren and Schiel, 2008; Troost et al., 2010; Wijsman and Smaal, 2011), obtaining in-situ data (in order to feed the models) is expensive. Current methods of spatially interpolating point data of food variables cannot always be trusted for an entire estuary or bay, since tidal currents, depth and in some areas resuspension of benthic phytoplankton are causes for spatial variability. Point data is in some cases not considered representative for specific culture site conditions. These reasons lead to an underutilization of shellfish production models, especially by shellfish producers. Using spatio-temporal data of food variables from EO might lead to cheaper input data and therefore an increase in the utilization, applicability and the value of shellfish growth and production models. Naturally proper validation is required to ensure the required high quality.

7.2 Background

7.2.1 Mussel growth

Growth and growth rate of mussels is primarily linked to water temperature and food availability. The spatial and temporal heterogeneity of food quantity and quality in coastal regions depends on velocity (mostly affected by tidal currents), wave action, depth and resuspension of benthic phytoplankton. Mussels are known to adapt their feeding behaviour to changes in their environment, for example by adjusting filtration rates in order to optimize food intake (Bayne *et al.*, 1993). Food intake and the processes of assimilation and respiration are, in turn, influenced by temperature. Increase in water temperature will increase the rate of these processes and hence result in growth acceleration. Peak growth rate of mussels in Dutch coastal waters takes place during spring season, when phytoplankton blooms and water temperatures are rising above 10°C.

7.2.2 DEB theory

Processes of assimilation and respiration resulting in energy uptake, growth and reproduction are described in Dynamic Energy Budget (DEB) models (Kooijman, 2010) as a function of the organisms' environment (e.g. temperature and food variables). It is a theory that is widely applied to different species by using species specific parameters, and has become increasingly popular for modelling shellfish development (Bacher and Gangnery, 2006; Pouvreau *et al.*, 2006; Bourlès *et al.*, 2009; Troost *et al.*, 2010; Wijsman and Smaal, 2011; Chowdhury *et al.*, 2019). The basic DEB model structure is generic and flexible, and requires a relatively small number of parameters. The forcing conditions for most DEB shellfish models are water temperature and one or more quantifiers for food. Chlorophyll-a and/or Total Suspended Matter (TSM) is often used to estimate the food available for shellfish and are considered reliable food quantifiers for DEB models for bivalves (Pouvreau *et al.*, 2006; Troost *et al.*, 2010; Wijsman and Smaal, 2011). In situ measurements of Chl-a, TSM and water temperature used in modelling shellfish growth with DEB theory are largely based on point sampling (e.g. Sara *et al.* 2012; Lavaud 2014; Ren & Schiel 2008), but the value of using satellite derived environmental data as forcings in shellfish DEB models is recognized (Thomas *et al.*, 2011). Modelling spatiotemporal variability in growth of blue mussels, using the DEB theory with food and temperature derived from Sentinel-3 (S3), delivers a product to predict spatially explicit shellfish performance for Dutch users in order to optimize production efficiency.

7.2.3 Study areas

The Dutch government has regulated farming of blue mussels to specific sites in the Netherlands. On these culture sites, located in the western Wadden Sea and the Oosterschelde estuary (Figure 27), traditional mussel farming practices are carried out. This involves seeding of juvenile mussels on bottom plots and growing them in the natural environment until consumption size is reached.

The Dutch part of the Wadden Sea in the north of the Netherlands covers 2500 km². The Wadden Sea is divided from the North Sea by a range of narrow islands, and in between connected through tidal channels that distribute water through a network of gullies. The Wadden Sea is a dynamic and shallow area, and half of it consists of intertidal flats, creating a turbid environment. Most of the mussel cultivation sites are located in the western Wadden Sea, covering roughly 7700 ha (Capelle, 2017). Two tidal channels, Marsdiep and Vliestroom contribute to the majority of seawater exchange in the western part of the Wadden Sea.

The Oosterschelde is a low dynamic estuary located in the Rhine-Meuse-Scheldt delta covering 350 km² in the south-western part of the Netherlands. A storm surge barrier was placed in the mouth of the estuary in 1987 allowing tidal influence, but the estuary was isolated from river input as well, turning it from a turbid estuary into a sheltered tidal bay with minor fresh water influence. 2250 ha of mussel culture plots are located in the Oosterschelde estuary.

Figure 27 Mussel farming areas in red in the Netherlands: the Wadden Sea in the North and the Oosterschelde estuary in the South west.

Almost all mussel farming takes place in subtidal areas. Farmers report differences in mussel growth between the different sites (Figure 27) and are interested in ways to manage their farming practices to sustain a profitable income. This calls for a need to identify the spatial patterns and differences in growth. The generic concept of a DEB model for shellfish and EO data provides a product that can potentially be used for culture sites elsewhere.

Figure 28 Example of spatial variation in mussel growth patterns (shell length) in the Wadden Sea 2017 (data from Innopro, 2017)

7.3 Input data

7.3.1 CoastObs basic products

Spatio-temporal raster data of:

- S3 Chl-a
- S3 TSM
- Sea Surface Temperature (SST) (only for the DEB model simulation)

7.3.2 Additional data

A dataset of standardized mussel growth from the project INNOPRO, funded by the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund, was used as in situ validation data for the models.

7.4 Methods

This higher-level product to identify and model the spatial dynamics in mussel growth consists of a two step approach. First to use aggregates of S3 derived food variables Chl-a and TSM combined with mussel growth data of 2017 and 2018 to indentify the main predictor for growth in both of the study areas. The second approach integrates CoastObs basic products with the DEB theory to model spatial temporal variation in growth and to predict spatially explicit shellfish performance for Dutch users in order to optimize production efficiency.

7.4.1 Mussel growth potential maps

Since the highest growth rates of mussels occur during spring blooms of phytoplankton, the first step was to create maps of spring season averages of food variables Chl-a and TSM. The maps were based on instantaneously processed data from single satellite acquisition (see 7.4.3 Satellite data). OLS regression was used in each study area for years 2017 and 2018 to find correlations between log transformed values of food variables from S3 data and field measurements of mussel growth in shell length. For the used dataset on mussel growth, see 7.4.4 Validation data.

Areas covered by clouds or presenting other disturbances in individual S3 images were removed, resulting in Chl-a and TSM maps with sometimes scattered pixels. To extract enough values for each field station where mussel growth was measured (Figure 30), the pixels within an area of 1 km² around the gully where the mussel monitoring station was located were averaged as a proxy for Chl-a and TSM at each location. The averages for the spring seasons of the years 2017 as 2018 were calculated (for the Oosterschelde estuary: N=14 and N=16, for the Wadden Sea N=21 and N=22 for 2017 and 2018 respectively). Following the recommendation of Hawkins et al. (1996), the ratio of organic content relative to total suspended matter is sometimes more indicative for growth than just food concentration, therefore, the variable Food Quality was added by calculating the Chl-a/TSM ratio.

Based on the main spatial growth predictors from the fitted regression model for both the study areas, maps were generated indicating shellfish growth potential. Analysis and generation of maps was done using R-software.

7.4.2 DEB model simulation

A standard DEB model developed by Wijsman (2019) was used here, describing energy flow in mussels focusing on food assimilation and utilization for maintenance, growth and reproduction. The parameter set for *Mytilus edulis* specifically adapted for Dutch cultivation areas was also derived from Wijsman (2019). Simulations were conducted using an R-script, computing daily energy flows as a function of temperature (SST in degrees Celsius) and the food related variables Chl-a and TSM. From the S3 basic products, time series for SST, Chl-a and TSM were extracted for each pixel coordinate (resolution 300x300m) in the study areas Oosterschelde and western Wadden Sea. Missing values in time series resulting from missing images or cloud covered pixels were interpolated linearly to create a daily sequence and used as forcing in the model. The model was run for both 2017 and 2018 from April-October, starting with mussel seed sizes of 3.0 and 3.6 cm for 2017 and 2018, respectively. The model was then calibrated by adjusting the half saturation coefficient for food uptake for the different regions within a study area. This coefficient can be seen as a measure of food quality. The workflow steps are visualised in Figure 29. Since depth was expected to influence the confidence of food variable data, and consequently the model simulations, we omitted locations shallower than 1.5 meter (average tidal amplitude in Dutch coastal areas) during the validation step. Evaluation of goodness of fit was done by linear regression between observations in shell length (cm) and simulated length. The first values were excluded. The resulting model was tested against a slope=1 model with an alpha threshold of 0.05.

Figure 29 Overview of inputs, pre-processing and simulation workflow

7.4.3 Satellite data

All Sentinel-3 images from April – October 2017 and 2018 covering the two study areas were

downloaded as Level 1 full resolution non time critical products in a batch mode from the Copernicus API. All the data were processed using SNAP's graphical processing tool (GPT) and Python for automation. The processing steps consisted of:

- Subsetting to the area of interest (AOI) in order to achieve faster processing speeds.
- Calculation of flags using Idepix which is a cloud detection algorithm included in the SNAP toolbox.
- Atmospheric correction, using the C2RCC-v2 algorithm (Brockmann et al., 2016). This version was tested for the Wadden Sea (HBOTE project) and out-performed other atmospheric correction algorithms.
- Chl-a calculation using the Gons (2005) algorithm. At this step, all the invalid pixels were removed.
- TSM calculation was done using Nechad's algorithm using the 705nm band.
- Reprojection of the dataset into WGS84.

This approach was validated within the SBIR project HBOTE (flyer, in Dutch). S3 Chl-a and TSM concentrations have partially been validated against in situ measurements

Sea Surface Temperature (SST) was downloaded from the GHRSSST dataset: GHRSSST stands for: Group for High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature). The data were downloaded from the Physical Oceanography Distributed Active Archive Center API. This is a Level 4 global dataset with code name: MUR-JPL-L4-GLOB-v4.1. More details about the derivation of this dataset can be found in this link: <https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/dataset/MUR-JPL-L4-GLOB-v4.1>

The post-processing steps were:

- Reprojection of the dataset into WGS84.
- Subsetting to our AOI and to the SST band.

7.4.4 Validation data

A dataset of mussel growth measurements in the field was obtained from INNOPRO (2018) - funded by the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund - where growth of blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) was measured from April to October in 2017 & 2018 at 12 locations in the Wadden Sea and 12 locations in the Oosterschelde (Figure 30).

Similar sized mussels (3.0 ± 0.2 cm for 2017 and 3.6 ± 0.2 cm for 2018) were placed in a unit containing six compartments. Each compartment was filled with 80 mussels at the beginning of

the monitoring period and each month one compartment was emptied and mussels were analysed for length and wet weight. Length of all individual mussels was measured using a digital calliper (accuracy of 0.01 mm) and averaged for each location. Growth rate for length (mm.day⁻¹) at each location was expressed by the change in average length during a sampling interval divided by the number of days.

No	Oosterschelde station name
1	Hammen 9
2	Hammen 68C
3	Hammen 174
4	Hammen 184
5	Hammen 102
6	OSWD11
7	OSWD 185
8	OSWD 200
9	OSWD 81
10	Mastgat 6/7
11	Mastgat 22
12	ZK 3

No	Wadden Sea station name
1	Texel 7
2	Vlieter 94
3	Scheurrak 47
4	Slenk 14A
5	Meep 12
6	Inschot 57
7	Balgen 27
8	Meep 49
9	Oosterom 1B
10	Oosterom 2
11	Oosterom 14
12	Oosterom 20C

Figure 30 Mussel growth monitoring stations in the Oosterschelde estuary (top) and the Wadden Sea (bottom)

7.5 Results

7.5.1 Mussel growth potential maps

Many studies have related food concentration, expressed as chlorophyll-a as a proxy for food quantity to mussel growth (Page and Hubbard, 1987; Grizzle *et al.*, 2006; Wijsman, 2017). Regression results based on CoastObs standard products show that this is not primarily the case in Dutch study areas (Table 7). The primary contributors to variation in spring growth, although weak, are Total Suspended Matter for the Oosterschelde estuary (negatively correlated) and food quality for the Wadden Sea, which is positively correlated to growth. Composition of total suspended matter influences the feeding behaviour of mussels (Bayne *et al.* 1987), and feeding behaviour is indirectly linked to growth. High total suspended matter concentrations causes mussels to put more energy into separating edible food particles from silt and other non-edible parts, which costs energy that otherwise might be invested in growth (Hawkins *et al.*, 1996).

Table 7 Main predictors for mussel growth rates in each study area

Study area	Main predictor	Parameter estimate	R ²	p-value
Oosterschelde	log Total Suspended Matter	-0.02	0.24	0.009
	log Food Quality	0.03	0.17	0.025
Wadden Sea	log Food Quality	0.12	0.31	0.013

Figure 31 and Figure 32 show mussel growth potential maps of the two Dutch study areas based on the main predicting S3 basic product food variables. The general pattern in the growth potential map for the Wadden Sea (Figure 31) shows a chance for better growth rate closer to the entrance of the tidal channels. The further into the estuary the lower growth rates get, related with TSM availability in those areas, decreasing food quality and hence growth potential.

Figure 31 Mussel growth potential for spring in the Wadden Sea, rectangular shapes indicate shellfish cultivation plots, white areas are intertidal flats and grey areas indicate land. Mussel growth is expressed in $\text{mm}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$.

Growth potential in the Oosterschelde estuary (Figure 32) is highest close at the entrance of the estuary, and closer to the shore. This is also where the tidal channels are located. The shallower areas in the middle of the estuary generally have higher TSM due to resuspension of bottom particles.

Figure 32 Mussel growth potential for spring in the Oosterschelde estuary, rectangular shapes indicate shellfish cultivation plots. Mussel growth is expressed in $\text{mm}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$.

Growth potential maps based on the main predictors from linear regression with S3 basic product averages of food variables as discussed in this section, are useful to explain spatial variability and to predict seasonal growth. Regression results are not that strong (table 7), but maps can be used as a guideline to indicate the potential within a specific study area.

7.5.2 Spatio temporal DEB model of mussel growth

Growth potential maps based on spatio-temporal DEB model simulations forced with SST, Chla and TSM are more specific than the approach used in 7.5.1 and output can be derived for multiple timescales to suit users' wishes. According to the initial analysis of mussel growth predictors (7.5.1), food quality is important for mussel growth in the Wadden Sea. The half saturation constant X_k parameter in the DEB model can be seen as a measure of food quality

and is mentioned to be diet- and environment specific (Pouvreau et al., 2006; Bourlès et al., 2009; Alunno-Bruscia et al., 2011). Therefore, differences in growth between areas might be related to differences in food quality. We adjusted the half saturation coefficient X_k in the calibration process –based on in situ data- to fit the different areas in the Wadden Sea (Figure 33) Since most of the water exchange and thus food exchange in the Wadden Sea is driven by tidal currents, we used the major tidal channels to identify areas for X_k values. An X_k value of 0.75 was set in the north, which is fed by the northern branch of the tidal channel called Vliestroom, the area around the southern branch of Vliestroom was set at 2. The area around the tidal channel in the south, called Marsdiep was set to an X_k value of 3. Even though X_k was adjusted to fit the different areas around the tidal channels in the Wadden Sea, the model gave a slight underestimation for both years of simulation compared to observed mussel length, with an overall R^2 of 0.82 (Figure 34, right side).

Figure 33 Partitioning of the X_k parameter (half saturation constant for food) areas in the Wadden Sea during calibration steps.

Figure 34 Simulations plotted against observations of shell length (cm) for mussels cultivated in the Oosterschelde estuary and the Wadden Sea. Open circles represent 2017 data, black circles 2018 data.

Table 8 Comparison between observed and simulated results for length for both study areas in 2017 and 2018: slope of the regression, coefficient of determination (R^2), and p value for slope = 1

Study area	Year	Slope	R^2	p-value for slope = 1
Oosterschelde	2017	0.85	0.85	0.001
	2018	1.02	0.83	0.696
Wadden Sea	2017	0.87	0.69	0.043
	2018	0.89	0.89	0.035

Since spatial variation in growth for the Oosterschelde estuary was not as large as in the Wadden sea, a single value of $X_k = 0.5$ was used. Validation results for the Oosterschelde show an overall coefficient of determination of 0.85 (Figure 34) with no significant difference between observation and simulated results in 2018 (table 8). Using a single half saturation coefficient (X_k) value as measure for food quality, does not correct for the higher growth rates (steeper slopes) in the spring season May to July, as is the case for many validation locations (Figure 35).

Figure 35 Temporal simulations of mussel growth (increase in length - cm) at twelve locations in the Oosterschelde estuary in 2018. Observed growth is indicated with a blue line and simulated growth with a red line. For locations see Figure 30

Outputs of the simulation DEB model were also spatialized to both study areas (Figure 36 and 37). It can be observed that the months with higher expected growth correspond to June and July, probably related with a higher water temperature and higher mussel assimilation rates.

Figure 36 Example of monthly aggregates from DEB model outputs transformed to relative growth rate (length increase in %) for the Wadden Sea.

Figure 37 Map example of specific growth potential at the designated shellfish plots, relative to the average growth in the Wadden Sea based on multi year data.

7.6 User feedback

Initial higher level products of mussel growth potential have been presented on February 22 and April 18, 2019 to an audience with users. The most important initial feedback was the discrepancy of results in areas bordering intertidal flats in both study areas. Our model predicted high growth rates, while farmers found low mussel growth. Based on this observation we decided to omit validation data originating from locations shallower than 1.5 meter. Other designated user meetings will still be organized inside the frame of CoastObs.

7.7 Conclusions and recommendations

The integration of S3 spatial raster data of food variables and water temperature with an existing DEB model provide promising results. Model output represented in different types of maps as higher level product provide useful information for shellfish farmers and the mussel producers organisation active in the Dutch case study areas:

Monthly maps of growth potential generated from the DEB model based on multi year averages of food and temperature conditions in the study areas provide farmers with information that can be used to strategically plan and manage mussel batches throughout different shell fish plots. Maps like these can also contribute to the selection of new cultivation areas in an estuary, provided that other necessary culture specific conditions are met.

Maps indicating growth potential on plot level relative to average growth in the area has proven to be possible based on CoastObs S3 basic products (e.g. Figure 34). These maps can even identify within shellfish plot growth variation.

Thus far, only data from 2017 and 2018 has been used to create higher level products based on multiyear aggregates during this exercise. Uncertainties in the models are expected to be reduced as more data becomes available.

Time series of food variables derived from S3 images lack the typical seasonal spring bloom pattern, resulting in an underestimation of simulated growth in the months May/June compared to field observations. Food quality in spring is expected to be better than during summer and fall, and using a single X_k value does not account for this phenomenon. Seasonal interpolation of input food variables based on long year averages from the Dutch National Monitoring Network (waterinfo.nl) to mimic the typical phytoplankton blooms during spring however did not improve the fit of the model.

S3 derived data of food variables and temperature in the Wadden Sea and the Oosterschelde estuary can partially explain spatial variability in mussel growth during high growth rates in spring, with food quality being the most important parameter in the Wadden Sea and Total Suspended Matter in the Oosterschelde. Since a generic algorithm is used for chlorophyll-a and total suspended matter for both case studies -which differ in dynamics and turbidity-, higher level products are expected to benefit from improved area specific algorithms. Improved algorithms might include the expected seasonal pattern in food variables as well. Water samples of both Dutch study areas have been collected throughout 2018 and sampling is still on-going. Validation results will be included in D3.10, and used to also determine the level of confidence in the higher level products. Depth for example has proven to influence spatial growth variation (e.g. Figure 31 and 32) and DEB model simulation results. Shallow areas are in

general higher in temperature than deeper parts, thus increasing the mussels' ability in the model to take up food. S3 derived food variables in shallow areas might either be influenced by bottom visibility or increased turbidity due to resuspension of sediment. Both situations can lead to overestimate food availability and, then, a significant overestimation of growth as the model showed. Besides area specific algorithms for Chl-a and TSM, a confidence layer becomes necessary, since most of the shellfish plots are located on the edges of tidal gullies with a steep gradient towards the shallower intertidal flats. Addressing this issue will deal with the initial user feedback and improve model fit and higher level product quality.

Further user feedback will be obtained in upcoming user meetings, and higher level products will be improved according to the users' needs. Data collected from April - October 2019 will provide an extra year of validation data, which will be included during the improvement phase.

8 Integration with modelling: harmful algae bloom forecasting

8.1 Rationale

The occurrence of Harmful Algae Blooms (HABs) in Galicia cause an important ecological damage and a strong economic impact, since mussel production areas are closed to places where toxins are detected. HABs detection methods using colour satellite images and forecasting models based on environmental parameters may complement traditional monitoring systems based on field samplings. These products are cost-effective and provide a synoptic view of the study area with a good spatial resolution and temporal coverage. They are of great interest to both monitoring authorities and aquaculture producers. Higher-level species indicators for *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. and *Alexandrium minutum* and a forecasting system for amnesic shellfish poisoning (ASP) closures due to blooms of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. are described in the next sections.

8.2 Background

8.2.1 Harmful Aalgae Blooms (HABs) in Galicia

The south-west coast of Galicia (NW Spain) is characterized by the presence of the Rias Baixas, four large flooded river valleys with a complex coastal dynamic, since these coastal embayments are affected by strong tides, natural and anthropogenic freshwater inputs and especially the upwelling-downwelling cycle (Barton *et al.*, 2015).

The Rias Baixas are highly productive and biodiverse environments because of the introduction of deep, cold, nutrient-rich waters during the upwelling events associated with northern winds occurring mainly between May and September. In addition to the commercial exploitation of natural fish and shellfish resources, the mussel aquaculture using floating rafts, called *bateas*, is one of the most important economic activities in the region, being Galicia the leading mussel producer in Europe (Labarta & Fernández-Reiriz, 2019).

Massive proliferations of toxic microalgae, which are usually known as Harmful Algae Blooms (HABs), are a recurring event in the Galician coast. HABs cause damage to the *rias* ecosystems and may imply a risk to human health. Moreover, if toxins are detected, mussel production areas are closed causing a strong socio-economic impact (González Vilas *et al.*, 2014; Rodríguez *et al.*, 2011). Closures mainly occur when three different types of toxins associated with HABs

are detected: Lipophilic Shellfish Toxins (LST), due to *Dinophysis* spp.; Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP), caused by *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp.; and Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP), which could be related to *Gymnodinium catenatum* or *Alexandrium minutum* (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2011).

8.2.2 HABs monitoring methods

Traditional HABs monitoring systems are based on direct observations, i.e., samplings at field stations and subsequent laboratory processing of samples, including phytoplankton species identification, cell count of toxic species using optical microscopy or toxin chemical analysis (Anderson, 2009). Although direct observations are essential and irreplaceable, different authors have proposed approaches based on indirect observations, such as satellite colour images and/or environmental parameters (Blondeau-Patissier *et al.*, 2014; Kudela *et al.*, 2017).

Map products based on colour satellite images providing useful information for HABs detection and monitoring in Galicia coasts, including Chl-a regional algorithms and species indicators, are described in detail in Deliverable 3.6. As compared to traditional methods, these products are cost-effective and provide a more synoptic view of the study area.

Regarding the use of environmental parameters, numerous studies have focused on gaining a deeper insight into the relationships between the characteristics of the environment and the distribution and/or the toxin production of a species. For instance, different authors have identified nutrient availability, temperature, salinity, photoperiod or light intensity as factors controlling abundance, bloom dynamic and toxicity of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. (Downes-Tettmar *et al.*, 2013; Liefer *et al.*, 2013; Bargu *et al.*, 2016; Tas & Lundholm, 2017; Thorel *et al.*, 2017; Pednekar *et al.*, 2018). Relationships between *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. and indirect indicators of nutrient availability, as river flow, precipitation or upwelling indices, have also been found (Palma *et al.*, 2010; Schnetzer *et al.*, 2013; González Vilas *et al.*, 2014).

Application of statistical techniques based on a set of input variables for the prediction of HABs has been also extensively studied (Anderson *et al.*, 2010; Volf *et al.*, 2011). Other authors have proposed the use of machine learning methods because of their capability to work with complex and non-linear data, including fuzzy logic (Blauw *et al.*, 2006), artificial neural networks (Lee *et al.*, 2003) or support vector machines (SVM) (Gogaraju *et al.*, 2011; González Vilas *et al.*, 2014).

Some authors have also incorporated satellite data into the prediction models. For instance, Stumpf *et al.* (2009) describe an operational forecast system in Southwest Florida (USA) for *Karenia brevis* blooms, using ocean colour images, wind data and a rule-based model derived from field observations of bloom extension and location. Anderson *et al.* (2009) developed regression models for *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. abundance in Santa Barbara channel

integrating ocean colour (MODIS-Aqua and SeaWiFS) and sea surface temperature (AVHRR) data. The CoastObs higher-level products integrates the HABs basic products with environmental data to provide a better fit to the user's needs.

8.3 Input data

8.3.1 CoastObs HABs products for the Galician case study

A set of HABs products based on S3 images were developed within CoastObs (see Deliverable 3.6 for more details). All these products are specific for the Galician water case study and allow users to obtain reliable and accurate maps of different parameters related to HABs detection in the *rias*. Specifically, the following HABs products are used as input for higher-level products described in this chapter:

- Chl-a: Chl-a maps are generated from S3 images using the cluster-specific regional algorithms described in Deliverable 3.6 (Section 3).
- Special indicator for *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp.: Bloom probability or bloom/no bloom maps for *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. are derived from S3 images using the Support Vector Machine (SVM) probability model described in Deliverable 3.6 (Section 4.2).
- Special indicator for *Alexandrium minutum*: Presence probability, presence/absence, abundance and bloom probability maps for *Alexandrium minutum* based on S3 images are obtained using the SVM probability model described in Deliverable 3.6 (Section 4.3).

8.3.2 Additional data

8.3.2.1 INTECMAR monitoring programme

The Technological Institute for the Control of the Marine Environment of Galicia (INTECMAR) conducts a routine monitoring programme based on a weekly sampling at 41 stations distributed along the Galician coast. It monitors HABs and marine biotoxins, and regulate the closure of mussel production areas if required to comply with the application of the administrative regulations and the sanitary requirements. Figure 38 shows the 41 INTECMAR sampling stations and the 22 mussel production areas. Note that each area includes several raft polygons, summing a total of 52. A total of 3610 rafts are distributed across these polygons, so that each polygon contains a number of rafts ranging from only 3 to 267.

Figure 38 a) Map of the Rias Baixas showing the location of the INTECMAR sampling stations. b) Map showing the mussel production areas and the raft polygons.

The following parameters available from INTECMAR are useful for the development and validation of the higher level products described in this chapter:

- Temperature and salinity: They are measured *in situ* using a Seabird 25 or a Seabird 19plus CTD instrument. Profiles between surface and a meter above bottom are obtained at each station.
- Chl-a: Chl-a concentrations are estimated by spectrofluorometry using the method proposed by Zapata *et al.* (2000) for pigment separation and extraction. Integrated water samples collected at three depth ranges (0 m – 5 m; 5 m – 10 m and 10 m – 15 m) are processed at each sampling station.

- Inorganic nutrients: Concentrations of nitrate, nitrite, phosphate and silicate are estimated using Bran-Luebbe Quattro and Traacs auto-analysers following the continuous segmented flow analysis method initially proposed by Hansen & Grassoff (1983).
- Phytoplankton abundance: Phytoplankton data are collected at each station using phytoplankton tow nets (10 μm mesh) from surface to 15 meters depth. Samples are fixed with formaldehyde 4% and stored under dark and cool conditions. Total abundances (in cells L^{-1}) of different species, including *Alexandrium* spp. and *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp., are counted using an inverted light microscope at 250x and 400x magnification (Utermöhl, 1958).
- Closure of mussel production areas: Closure data for each production area are recorded using a code indicating the reason of the closure: **C**: Cautionary; **A**: Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP); **P**: Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP); **L**: Lipophilic shellfish toxins (LSTs). Single codes are also combined, e.g., C-A or L-P.

While temperature, salinity, Chl-a and inorganic nutrients are used as input, phytoplankton abundance and closure of production areas are the main output of the higher-level products. Chl-a concentrations and phytoplankton abundance are also required for the validation of HABs products (see section 8.3.1).

8.3.2.2 Dedicated CoastObs field campaigns

Two field campaigns were conducted in July 2018 and June 2019 in the Ria de Vigo, sampling a total of 158 stations on 20 different dates using two research vessels.

Data collected in these surveys are mainly contributing to the validation of CoastObs products. For instance, Chl-a concentration, coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM), size-fractionated chlorophyll and TSM were determined from triplicated water samples collected at each station from surface to 5 metres depth using a PVC hose. Specifically, Chl-a analysis is based on a high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method with a reverse phase C_8 (Zapata *et al.*, 2000).

Some water samples were also analysed by INTECMAR experts to obtain phytoplankton abundances of different species (e.g. *Alexandrium minutum* and *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp.).

8.3.2.3 Upwelling data

Upwelling indices are usually estimated using the Bakun's (1973) method from the average daily modulus and northward component of the wind in the continental shelf adjacent to the *rias*. Wind data can be collected from a meteorological station representative of the study area (e.g.

Cape Silleiro Seawatch buoy, see Herrera *et al.*, 2005), meteorological models or satellite scatterometers. Positive values are the result of favourable upwelling winds while negative indices are related to downwelling events.

We used 6-hourly upwelling indices routinely distributed by the Fleet Numerical Meteorology and Oceanography Center (FNMOC), which are based on data of the the Navy Operational Global Atmospheric Prediction System (NOGAPS) model (Gonzalez-Nuevo *et al.*, 2014). Data were available from the Spanish Oceanographic Institute (IEO) at <http://www.indicedeafloramiento.ieo.es/>.

In terms of HABs monitoring, the evolution of the upwelling index in the previous days provide more useful information. As a typical upwelling cycle lasts 10 days, we estimated a 10-days upwelling indicator (I_{W-10}) using FNMOC indices following the next steps for a given date:

- 1) Compute daily average positive and negative indices (note that indices are provided each 6 hours) for the last 10 days (from day -9 to day 0).
- 2) Compute the membership degree (between 0 and 1) to each one of the seven clusters defining typical oceanographic conditions during a 10 days' period. These clusters are: 1) upwelling strengthening; 2) upwelling event; 3) upwelling relaxation; 4) downwelling strengthening; 5) downwelling event; 6) downwelling relaxation; and 7) no wind.
- 3) Project the membership degree to each cluster in a polar coordinate system and define I_{W-10} as the resulting angle, varying between 0 and 360. Values are related to the oceanographic conditions in the last 10 days: upwelling (values from 22.5 to 157.5), downwelling (values from 202.5 to 337.5) and no wind (values from 157.5 to 202.5 and from 337.5 to 22.5).

The I_{W-10} was used as input of some of the higher-level products described in this chapter.

8.3.2.4 Oceanographic buoys

Oceanographic data, including temperature and salinity, were available from oceanographic buoys located at the mouths of the Ria de Muros (Muros buoy), Ria de Arousa (Ribeira buoy) and Ria de Vigo (Cies bouy). The network is managed by MeteoGalicia and the Raia observatory (<http://www2.meteogalicia.gal/galego/observacion/plataformas/plataformas.asp>).

Parameters were recorded every ten minutes, but we used the available daily averages. Both sea surface temperature and salinity were used as input of the higher-level products described in this chapter.

8.3.2.5 Meteorological stations

Different meteorological parameters, including precipitation, are available from the meteorological automatic station network managed by MeteoGalicia (<https://www.meteogalicia.gal/observacion/estacions/estacions.action>). Data were recorded every ten minutes, but daily averages were also available. We selected 52 stations located in the Galician-Coast river basin, covering the river network flowing into the *rias*. The average of the daily precipitation sum of all these stations for the last 10 days (P_{-10}) was computed as an indirect indicator of freshwater inputs and used as input of the higher-level products described in this chapter.

8.3.2.6 CMEMS products

The Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) provides a set of marine products and services including data from both observations and models (<http://marine.copernicus.eu/>).

Although the spatial resolution is low to derive accurate maps of the *rias*, CMEMS products could be useful as an alternative to INTECMAR or oceanographic buoy data for obtaining average daily values of some parameters. For instance, average sea surface temperature for a *ria* could be used as input of some of the higher-level products described in this chapter.

8.4 Methods

8.4.1 Higher-level *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. indicator

The output of the species indicator for *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. is a bloom probability map or a bloom/no bloom map, which are directly generated from a cloud-free S3 image by applying a SVM bloom probability model (For more details, see D3.6, Section 4.2). The higher-level *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. indicator integrates this basic indicator with a set of ancillary data (Table 9) and estimates the abundance of the species for each production area as output. Table 9 summarizes the required ancillary data showing the possible sources and their frequencies. Except for the nutrients concentrations, which were only available from the INTECMAR monitoring program, all the variables were provided on a daily basis.

Output abundances of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. are given in $\log_{10}[\text{cell/L}]$. In order to make the product results more readable and easy to interpret for final users (mainly mussel producers), a categorical output showing the bloom probability for each production area is proposed (Table 10). Categories were defined considering that blooms are usually identified as abundances over a threshold of 10^5 cells/L, i.e. a $\log_{10}[\text{cell/L}]$ value of 5 (Gonzalez Vilas *et al.*, 2014).

Table 9: Summary of the input variables required for the generation of the higher-level *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. species indicator.

Variable	Units	Sources	Frequency
Temperature [T]	°C	INTECMAR	Weekly
		Oceanographic buoys	Daily
		CMEMS	Daily
Salinity [S]	psu	INTECMAR	Weekly
		Oceanographic buoys	Daily
Chlorophyll a [Chl-a]	mg m ⁻³	Sentinel-3	Daily ¹
		INTECMAR	Weekly
		Oceanographic buoys	Daily
Phosphate [PO ₄ ³⁻]	μmol/L	INTECMAR	Weekly
Nitrate [NO ₃ ⁻]			
Nitrite [NO ₂ ⁻]			
Silicate [SiO ₄ ⁴⁻]			
10-days upwelling indicator [I _{W-10}]	-	FNMOCC (IEO)	Daily
10-days precipitation indicator [P ₋₁₀]	L/m ²	Meteorological stations	Daily

¹Chla concentration might only be estimated from cloud-free Sentinel-3 images.

Table 10: Bloom probability categories defined according to a set of ranges of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. abundances.

Abundances (Log10[cell/L])	Bloom probability
< 3	Very Low (0 %)
3-4	Low (25 %)
4-5	Medium (50 %)
5-5.5	High (75 %)
>5.5	Very High (100 %)

The approach to generate this higher-level product for a given date was based on the following steps:

- 1) Generation of a *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. bloom probability map for the Rias Baixas by applying the SVM model to a S3 cloud-free image (Figure 39a).
- 2) Bloom probabilities were spatial averaged for each production area (B_p) (Figure 39b). Only valid pixels within the production areas but outside the raft polygons were considered in the average computation.
- 3) Bloom probability for each production area were linked with the ancillary data. Daily average values for each *ria* were estimated in case of sea surface temperature, salinity, chl a and inorganic nutrients. The 10-days upwelling (I_{W-10} , see section 8.3.2.3) and precipitation (P_{AVG-10} , see section 8.3.2.5) indicators were computed for the image date.
- 4) Abundances of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. for each production area were estimated by applying a regression model using the bloom probability averages and the corresponding ancillary variables as input.
- 5) Abundances for each production area were converted into a single bloom probability value using the ranges defined in Table 10 (Figure 40).

Figure 39: a) *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. bloom probability map obtained from applying the SVM bloom prediction model to the Sentinel-3 image on 1 August 2018. b) Average bloom probability (B_p) and ancillary data extracted for the production area „Arousa 1”

Figure 40: Output of the higher-level *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. indicator on 1 August 2018.

8.4.2 *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. prediction product

The *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. prediction product was based on the SVM method developed by Gonzalez Vilas *et al.* (2014) for predicting blooms of this diatom in the Galician *rias*, but with some differences.

Firstly, closures of production areas due to ASP in a *ria* were defined as the output variable of the SVM models instead of using blooms defined in terms of abundance. Note that *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. is a genre including both non-toxic and toxic species and information about toxicity was not available. Hence, ASP closures were a best indicator in order to know if the detected species was a domoic acid (DA) producer causing toxic events.

Secondly, input data for a *ria* were defined between 1 and 5 days in advance with respect to the prediction date, i.e., SVM models used as input a set of environmental data for a given input date and obtain as output the ASP closure probability between 1 and 5 days later. The same input variables (Table 9) as used as ancillary data in the higher-level *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. indicator were selected for the development of different SVM models based on four different combinations of variables (see section 8.5.2 for details).

SVM foundations were explained in detail in the Deliverable 3.6 (section 2.4.2). SVM models were developed using the probability output and selecting the best parametric configuration by applying a 10-fold cross validation. The final SVM models were obtained by training the complete dataset using the optimal parameters.

The general approach to obtain the ASP closure probability prediction on a given input date consists of two steps:

- 1) Input data extraction: Variables used as input were summarized in Table 9. Daily averages were estimated for each *ria* for all the variables except for the 10-days upwelling and precipitation indicators, which were computed for the date and used for all the *rias*.
- 2) Modelling: SVM models were applied to obtain the ASP closure probability predicted for each *ria* between 1 and 5 days after the input date.

8.4.3 Higher-level *Alexandrium minutum* indicator

Basic *Alexandrium minutum* indicators based on S3 and S2 images were developed within CoastObs using data obtained during the bloom detected in the southern Rias Baixas (i.e. Vigo and Pontevedra) in summer 2018 (see Section 4.3 in D3.6 for more details). *Alexandrium minutum* is not a very common species on the Rias Baixas. The bloom observed in summer 2018 was associated with anomalously high sea surface temperatures (SST), as is observed in Figure 41, which shows the evolution of the average, minimal and maximal daily SST recorded on the Cies buoy during the bloom period. Average daily SST above 19°C and peaks between 21°C and 22°C were detected.

Figure 41: Evolution of the average, minimal and maximal sea surface temperatures (SST) recorded on the Cies buoy between June and July 2018 during the bloom of *Alexandrium minutum* in the Rias Baixas.

The higher-level *Alexandrium minutum* indicator integrates the basic indicator based on the SVM presence/absence model with SST data following the next steps:

- 1) Generation of a *Alexandrium minutum* presence probability map for the Rias Baixas from a cloud-free S3 image using the basic indicator based on the SVM presence/absence model (see section 4.3.1 in Deliverable 3.6).
- 2) Integration of the presence probability (Pp) derived from the basic indicator with SST data to build a final bloom/no bloom map, applying the following rule for each pixel:

Bloom: $Pp > 0.5$ and $SST > 19^{\circ}C$

No Bloom: $Pp \leq 0.5$ or $SST \leq 19^{\circ}C$

SST data could be derived from different sources, including SST maps provided by CMEMS or *in situ* data from INTECMAR or oceanographic buoys.

8.5 Results

8.5.1 Higher-level *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. indicator

A dataset consisting of 385 records was available for the development of the regression models. Each record includes the bloom probability for a given production area (Bp) computed from the

probability map obtained from the S3 image using the basic *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. indicator, a set of associated input variables for that date (Table 9) and the output variable, i.e. *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. abundances (in $\log_{10}[\text{cell/L}]$). Data were derived from 35 S3 images acquired between May 2016 and November 2018.

Four regression models using different variable combinations were developed (Table 11), so that the best model could be selected according to the availability of ancillary data.

Table 11: Combination of variables selected for the development of the regression models.

Regression model	Variables
A (all the variables)	Bp, T, S, Chl-a, PO_4^{3-} , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , SiO_4^{4-} , I_{W-10} , P_{-10}
B (optimized)	Bp, T, Chl-a, I_{W-10} , P_{-10}
C (basic)	Bp, I_{W-10} , P_{-10}
D (only basic indicator)	Bp

Performance measures for each regression model are summarized in Table 12 (see section 2.4.1 in Deliverable 3.6 for a description of these features).

Table 12: Performance measures for the different regression models

Model	R^2	MPE	VAR	$RMSE$	$ReRMSE$
A	0.61	0.00	0.36	0.60	38.95
B	0.59	0.00	0.38	0.62	39.45
C	0.53	0.00	0.45	0.67	40.99
D	0.46	0.00	0.51	0.71	42.29

All the regression models show a positive linear correlation between the abundances observed and predicted, with a mean prediction error (MPE) equal to zero, indicating that there is not overestimation or underestimation, and a root mean squared error ($RMSE$) lower than 1.

As expected, models including ancillary data (A, B and C) outperform the model D, which is only based on the bloom prediction derived from S3 image using the basic indicator.

Although the best performance results are achieved using all the variables (Model A), results from the optimized model (Model B) are only slightly worse, evidencing that nutrients concentrations and salinity show a lower relative contribution to estimate the *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. abundance. It could be explained because the relationships between abundances and nutrients concentrations are usually very complex due to two reasons: 1) natural populations are often composed of several species, and 2) there is a time delay between the maximum concentration of nutrients and the bloom development (Guannel *et al.*, 2015).

However, the 10-days precipitation (P_{-10}) and upwelling indicators (I_{W-10}), which are related to two factors (rainfall and upwelling-downwelling cycle) controlling the nutrient availability during the last 10 days, show a greater relative contribution. In fact, the basic model using only these parameters (Model C) is enough for improving the results from the model based only on the S3 images (Model D).

Figure 42 shows an example of the results obtained using the higher-level *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. indicator (Model A) for a series of S3 images acquired on summer 2016. These maps provide useful information in terms of temporal and spatial distribution. In this example, an extensive bloom is detected in the beginning of August in all the *rias* except Muros.

Figure 42: Results of the higher-level *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. indicator for a set of images in summer 2016: a) 18 July. b) 26 July. c) 1 August. d) 22 August. e) 5 September.

8.5.2 *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. prediction product

SVM models were developed using a dataset comprised of 1331 records, including environmental data for two periods: 2002-2012 (MERIS period) and 2016-2018 (S3 period). Each record corresponds to a specific date and *ria*.

Temperature, salinity, Chl-a and nutrients concentrations were available from INTECMAR, selecting data from external sampling stations as representative of the corresponding *ria* (V5

for Ria de Vigo, P4 for Ria de Pontevedra, A0 for Ria de Arousa, M5 for Ria de Muros-Noia, see Figure 38a). I_{W-10} and P_{-10} were computed for each date.

The output variable was defined according to the closures of production areas due to ASP. A *ria* is defined as "closed" on a given date if any of their production areas is affected by an ASP closure, and as "open" only if all their production areas are open.

Five datasets were built using as output the ASP closure between 1 and 5 days after the input date. All these datasets were unbalanced, since "close" records only represent 5% of the total.

A total of 20 SVM ASP closure models were developed using four combination of variables, which are shown in Table 13, and using as output the ASP closure between 1 and 5 days after the input date.

Table 13: Combination of variables selected for the development of the SVM ASP closure models.

SVM model	Variables
A	T, S, Chl-a, PO_4^{3-} , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , SiO_4^{4-} , I_{W-10} , P_{-10}
B	T, S, Chl-a, I_{W-10} , P_{-10}
C	chl-a, I_{W-10} , P_{-10}
D	I_{W-10} , P_{-10}

Table 14 shows the performance measures for the 20 SVM ASP closure models computed from the 10 fold cross-validation process used for the selection of the optimal parametric configuration. Except for the area under the curve (*AUC*), all the performance measures are derived from the confusion matrix (see section in Deliverable 3.6 for more details), i.e. overall accuracy (*OA*), true positive rate (*TPR*), true negative rate (*TNR*), false positive rate (*FPR*), false negative rate (*FNR*) and kappa statistic (κ). Since we worked with probability outputs (between 0 and 1), the confusion matrix was obtained using an optimal threshold maximizing the sum $TPR + TNR$.

Due to the unbalance of the datasets, *TNR* values are expected to be always greater than *TPR* values. However, there are not great differences between both values in most of the models, evidencing their robustness.

Comparing the different combinations of variables, the best results are always obtained using all the variables, including nutrients (Model A). In general, the basic models using only the 10-

days upwelling and precipitation indicators (Model D) produce poorer results and should be discarded in operational predictions.

Table 14: Performance measures computed from the leave-one-out cross-validation process for each SVM ASP closure model.

Output ASP Closure	Input Variables	<i>OA</i>	<i>TPR</i>	<i>TNR</i>	<i>FPR</i>	<i>FNR</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>AUC</i>
Day +1	A	0.79	0.70	0.79	0.30	0.21	0.78	0.83
	B	0.75	0.70	0.75	0.30	0.25	0.74	0.77
	C	0.57	0.78	0.56	0.22	0.44	0.56	0.68
	D	0.50	0.76	0.49	0.24	0.51	0.49	0.60
Day +2	A	0.86	0.69	0.87	0.31	0.13	0.85	0.84
	B	0.77	0.72	0.77	0.28	0.23	0.76	0.79
	C	0.67	0.62	0.67	0.38	0.33	0.66	0.69
	D	0.47	0.75	0.46	0.25	0.54	0.46	0.60
Day +3	A	0.88	0.58	0.90	0.42	0.10	0.88	0.87
	B	0.77	0.75	0.77	0.25	0.23	0.76	0.81
	C	0.60	0.69	0.60	0.31	0.40	0.59	0.68
	D	0.63	0.56	0.63	0.44	0.37	0.62	0.62
Day +4	A	0.89	0.65	0.90	0.35	0.10	0.89	0.86
	B	0.76	0.67	0.77	0.33	0.23	0.75	0.79
	D	0.82	0.46	0.84	0.54	0.16	0.82	0.62
	C	0.69	0.63	0.69	0.37	0.31	0.68	0.69
Day + 5	A	0.89	0.57	0.91	0.43	0.09	0.89	0.85
	B	0.75	0.73	0.75	0.27	0.25	0.74	0.79
	C	0.70	0.56	0.71	0.44	0.29	0.69	0.59
	D	0.60	0.56	0.60	0.44	0.40	0.59	0.54

Comparing the models using all the variables (Model A), the best global results are achieved in Day +3 (higher *AUC* value), and in Day +4 and +5 (higher *k* value). These models predict correctly between 57% and 70% of the ASP closures with a false alarm rate (*FNR*) between 9% and 21%.

Due to the unbalance in the dataset, a good capability to detect ASP closures implies a higher false alarm rate, i.e. models with higher *TPR* show also higher *FNR* (for instance, Model A, Day +1).

As expected, results of the final SMV models applied to the dataset are better than the obtained ones from the cross-validation. For instance, Figure 43 shows the results of this prediction system (Model A, Day +3) for the Ria de Muros in a period between 2004 and 2005. The model is able to predict correctly all the ASP closures (i.e. ASP closure probability above the optimal model threshold) with only two false alarms.

Figure 43: ASP closure probability observed (0: closed; 1: opened) and predicted using the SVM model A (day +3) for the Ria de Muros between 2004 and 2005.

8.5.3 Higher-level *Alexandrium minutum* indicator

The database for the development of the higher-level *Alexandrium minutum* indicator are limited to 70 records derived from 5 images acquired between 28 May and 1 August, 2018. Only 7 records with abundances greater than 10^5 cells L^{-1} were classified as bloom, while another 17 records show abundances above the detection limits. The species was only detected in the *rias* of Vigo and Pontevedra.

Figure 44 shows the SVM presence probability (Pp) versus the SST for each record in this database and the category (absence, presence or bloom) assigned according to the observed abundances.

Figure 44: SVM presence probability versus SST for each record in the *Alexandrium minutum* database. Colours show the category (absence, presence or bloom) defined according to the observed abundance.

The basic *Alexandrium minutum* indicator only identifies correctly 4 of 7 blooms with 4 false alarms. However, the higher-level indicator combining Pp and SST is able to identify correctly 6 of 7 blooms (Pp>0.5 and SST>19°C, see Figure 8.7) with only two false alarms.

Figure 45: Bloom/No bloom map on 17 July 2018 for *Alexandrium minutum* based on the Sentinel-3 image using: a) Basic indicator. b) Higher-level indicator integrating SST data.

Figure 45 compares a bloom/no bloom map derived from the basic indicator (see Section 4.3.1 in Deliverable 3.6 for details) and from the higher-level indicator integrating SST. The area identified as bloom is remarkable lower using the higher-level indicator, resulting in a map more consistent with the abundances recorded *in situ*. Therefore, integration of SST improves the *Alexandrium minutum* indicator based on Sentinel-3 images reducing the false alarm rate.

8.6 User feedback

All the CoastObs products and services are being developed in accordance with the final users. The users in Galicia are the Cooperative of Fishing Ship Owners of Vigo (ARVI) and the Regulatory Council of Mussel from Galicia. Therefore, the higher-level products will be also evaluated and improved according to the user's feedback. User evaluation will start in autumn 2019 and will last to the end of the project in October 2020. Results will be included in the service assessment report (D5.4).

8.7 Conclusions and recommendations

The higher-level *Pseudo-nitzschia spp.* indicator improved the basic indicator providing a better fit to the user's needs considering two aspects:

- Due to their lack of experience in managing raster maps products, users prefer simplified output formats. Therefore, a categorical output value showing the *Pseudo-nitzschia spp.* bloom probability is provided for each production area. The users, mainly mussel producers, are used to work with these areas, so that it is easier for them to compare the product with information from the INTECMAR monitoring program or other sources.
- The integration of the *Pseudo-nitzschia spp.* species indicator maps derived from S3 images with auxiliary data defining the environmental conditions in previous days improved the accuracy and reliability of the results.

As the basic indicator, it provides an excellent temporal coverage, with a daily image. Product generation is mainly limited by the cloud cover and the availability of ancillary data, despite of different possible data sources are provided. Different models were proposed using different combination of variables, so that a simpler option could be used if any variable is not available.

The prediction product shows promising results, being its main advantage the temporal coverage, since it provides a daily prediction between 1 and 5 days after the input date. This information could be very useful for mussel producers in terms of decision-making.

Unfortunately, prediction model development was hindered by the limited information about verified ASP closures, which were only identified in 5% of the total records. In fact, due to technical limitations associated with the INTECMAR database, it is possible that some ASP closures were not correctly recorded if there was another type of toxin (mainly LST) in addition to DA. Another limitation using ASP closures is that the recorded period depends on an administrative decision and it is usually extended for safety reasons. Hence, this period does not correspond with the real toxic event. The best solution would be to use DA concentration in mussel extracts as output variable for the models. Unfortunately, DA data are not publicly available at present. If DA data are finally available by the end of the project, SVM prediction models could be significantly improved including this variable.

Regarding the higher-level *Alexandrium minutum* indicator, it provides a more accurate and reliable map as compared to the basic indicator. With a daily S3 image, the product is only limited in terms of temporal frequency by the cloud cover and the availability of SST data.

HABs higher-level products were developed using historical data and S3 images acquired between between May 2016 and November 2018. Therefore, all these products require a further validation using independent data, including *in situ* data from INTECMAR and the dedicated CoastObs field campaign conducted in June 2019. Note that algorithms could be improved during the validation phase. Validation results will be included in a validation report (D3.10) due in October 2019.

9 References

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